

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures in Greece

WP3 Country Dossier

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List of abbreviations

AMIF	Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CCAC	Closed Controlled Access Centres
CPT	European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment
DRW-MMA	Directorate of returns and withdrawals-MMA
EU	European Union
GAS	Greek Asylum Service
IOM	International Organization for Migration
ISF	Internal Security Fund
JRS	Joint Reintegration Services
MCP	Ministry of Citizen Protection
MMA	Ministry of Migration and Asylum
NCCBCS-MCP	National Coordinating Centre for Border Control and Surveillance-MCP
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OCAVRR	Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
PEC	Pre-Embarkation Check
PRDC	Pre-Removal Detention Center
RIC	Reception and Identification Center
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructure
SIS	Schengen Information System
TCN	Third-Country National
WP	Work Package

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Summary

This Country Dossier focusing on Greece is part of Work Package 3 of the GAPs project and discusses how return migration governance is put into practice, through the concept of 'Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)'. Greece has a long history of returns the implementation of which has taken different forms depending on the political and socioeconomic context. Forced returns and deportations have been in place since the migratory movements of the 1990s, the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) was launched in 2010, and land and sea pushbacks have seen an important increase since 2019-2020.

The Country Dossier provides an overview of the three RMIs in Greece (AVRR, forced removals, and pushbacks) and an extended focus on AVRR. The methods included i) desk research and the creation of three flow maps on the RMIs in Greece; ii) the implementation of sixteen semi-structured interviews with stakeholders related both to AVRR and to other RMIs in Greece; and iii) the ethnographic tools of field visits, guided tours and observation at the IOM headquarters in Athens, the Open Centre for migrants registered for AVRR (OCAVRR), and the Athens International Airport during a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees.

The analysis unfolds the everyday modes of implementation of the RMIs and particularly the AVRR program in Greece by discussing the actors involved, their practices/'doings', the materials and technologies used, the relationships between the above, and several 'gaps' or other challenging issues. A wide network of involved actors emerges operating across multiple scales, such as those either facilitating or contesting returns, others maintaining a dual role, actors with an entrepreneurial approach to the returns' operation, and non-state and private actors. Moreover, as the analysis indicates, the implementation of returns is inherently non-linear. AVRR implementation comprises, on one hand, a seemingly standardised and uniform procedure for all, while, on the other, a 'case-by-case' and individualised framework. This results in different –and usually unequal– overall return experiences for immigrants, depending on their legal status, possession of identification and travel documents, vulnerabilities, entry points to the program, places of stay while awaiting return, and varying types of encounters with relevant authorities. Crucially, registration and participation in AVRR do not preclude the possibility of arrest and detention of migrants, even though they may possess documents that prove their enrolment in the program. Thus, as part of the different procedural steps, detention, the threat of detention, and processes of irregularisation remain fundamental components of the implementation of all RMIs and AVRR in particular, while implementing AVRR for detainees directly challenges its voluntary character. The latter is also questioned when the broader context in which AVRR operates in Greece is taken into account, highlighting that voluntary and forced returns should be understood as a continuum rather than a dichotomy, directly linked to multiplicity and non-linearity of migration trajectories. Funding, materials, geography, and technologies play a crucial role in shaping AVRR revealing its evolving and subject to change and expansion nature. The Country Dossier finally argues that a simultaneously organised and solid structure and a capacity for dynamic adaptation become evident in all RMIs, especially AVRR.

The GAPs Project

Return migration has become a policy priority across the world, especially in Europe. GAPs is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026)¹ that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of ‘return policymaking’. To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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¹ For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>

1. Introduction

This country dossier focusing on Greece is part of Work Package (WP) 3 of the GAPs project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is put into practice, through the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)’, by focusing on the so-called ‘crucial meso-level’ (cf. Faist, 2010). Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g. Xiang and Lindquist, 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (‘doings’), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape –i.e. facilitate or undermine and contest– the daily operation of returns. In doing so, the WP explores how the aforementioned work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground through a range of practices (Koinova et al., 2021). Moreover, WP3 investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMIs, namely assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks, by going beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness versus forced returns (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou, 2024). WP3 research was implemented in both European Union (EU) and non-EU countries, particularly in Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden, and Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. EU partner countries focus on RMIs returning people from the EU to either the EU –in the case of Dublin– or non-EU and non-EU partners focus on RMIs receiving returnees from the EU².

Greece has a long history of (formal and informal) return policies and practices that have taken different forms depending on the political and socioeconomic context. Forced returns and deportations have been taking place since the migratory movements of the 1990s. The Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program implemented by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) was launched in 2010. Land and sea pushbacks, which have been taking place since the 1990s with surges and declines, have seen an important increase during the 2015 so-called ‘refugee crisis’ and another surge from 2019 onwards, especially after the events in the Greek-Turkish border region of Evros in 2020.

The research conducted in Greece as part of WP3 focused on the AVRR program as a pivotal Return Migration Infrastructure. Additionally, the research also explored (albeit less in depth) forced removals and pushbacks. AVRR was chosen as a primary case study for different reasons: i) the lack of relevant research in Greece on this particular type of return, in contrast to other RMIs such as pushbacks which have attracted research and civil society interest; ii) the questions raised by the notion of ‘voluntariness’ of AVRR, especially when considering the Greek context, well-known for the limited integration opportunities, legal status restrictions, well-standing marginality and exclusions. In addition, a particular focus of the research has been on the Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (OCAVRR), a facility situated at a central location in Athens that drew our attention due to its material and spatial characteristics.

AVRR programs support migrants willing to return to their countries of origin and provide reintegration assistance upon return through financial and other means. In recent decades, assisted voluntary returns have emerged as a ‘tool of migration governance’ (Dennison, 2024) and AVRR, in particular, has gained prominence over other return programs. In Europe, AVRR has become a ‘central component’ of migration management in many countries (Kuschminder,

² In line with the GAPs research objectives, this Country Dossier primarily focuses on returns from Greece to the countries of origin, and on Greece as a country returning migrants. Returns to Greece mainly from Northern European countries under Dublin procedures are not included in the research. Yet, this remains a crucial issue to be investigated in the future.

2017). A common system for returns (voluntary or not) is envisioned in the EU Pact on Migration and Asylum and, within this framework, the European Commission has since 2021 communicated a Strategy on voluntary return and reintegration (COM, 2021; Dennison, 2024).

2. Methods

2.1 General methodological framework of WP3

The WP3 research was conducted between June 2023 and June 2024 and included two main tasks. First, creating an overview of RMIs in each partner country by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their practices/‘doings’, and iii) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on the selection of a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removals, or pushbacks) as a case study. The research started from a specific ‘entry point’ on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. It included the implementation of semi-structured interviews in each country with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure that may both facilitate and contest return operations. All interviewees received an Information Letter and provided either written or oral consent for participating in the research. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions, on a voluntary basis.

2.2 Specific conditions of data collection and analysis of the case study

In Greece, desk research started in June 2023, preliminary contacts were made in July 2023 and research on AVRR started in September 2023, while an ethics application was approved by EKKE’s Research Ethics Committee before the beginning of the research. The first ‘entry point’ was the Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (OCAVRR) in Athens, while soon the IOM headquarters in Athens emerged as another important entry point, illuminating the interrelations of spaces, materials, and procedures comprising the RMI.

WP3 research in Greece included 16 semi-structured interviews and one preliminary discussion with actors and stakeholders. The preliminary contacts with IOM foregrounded a range of different roles and responsibilities within AVRR, important for establishing a list of IOM interviewees. Gradually, the prospective interviewee list extended to include additional actors related also to other types of RMIs (such as forced removals and pushbacks).

Particularly, eight interviews were conducted with 11 IOM representatives, including the AVRR coordinators, team leaders of the information outreach, registration, operation, protection, re-integration departments, the medical unit, and the OCAVRR focal point in Athens, as well as outreach assistants in Thessaloniki. One interview was conducted with a representative of the Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MMA), and two with the independent authorities Greek Ombudsman (responsible for the External Audit of Forced Returns), and Greek National Commission for Human Rights (implementing a Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns/push backs). Two more interviews were conducted with Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) working on legal advocacy and human rights (Refugee Support Aegean–RSA, Greek Council for Refugees–GCR) and three with immigrant organisations including the Greek Forum of Refugees, the Pakistani

Community, and the Athens Georgian House/Georgian Sunday School. It should be mentioned that the Hellenic Police and several Embassies did not respond to our (e-mail and phone) multiple requests for an interview.

The research on AVRR employed diverse ethnographic methods including: i) field visits and a guided tour by IOM representatives at the IOM headquarters in Athens where most interviews also took place, ii) a guided tour at OCAVRR where interviews with AVRR & OCAVRR participants³ took place; and iii) observation of a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees at the El. Venizelos Athens International Airport. All necessary permissions (for the interviews and the field-visits) were granted by IOM and MMA, as the operating and the supervising authority for AVRR program in Greece, respectively. Overall, IOM's assistance was crucial for implementing this part of the research. Their professional collaboration and willingness to contribute to our research set up the field and became an invaluable source of data.

³ Interviews with immigrants, including AVRR and OCAVRR participants, were implemented in the context of the Work Package 7 of GAPs 'Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants'. Their experiences, practices and perceptions are discussed and analyzed in the WP7 Country Dossier of Greece (Papatzani et al., 2025).

3. Context

3.1 Context of migration

Greece transformed from an emigration to a destination country mainly in the 1990s, due to migrant arrivals from Balkan and Eastern European countries, predominantly Albania. Lacking an immigration policy, that decade was marked by intense policing, mass deportations, strict requirements for legal residence and regularisation procedures, and exploitation of the migrants' cheap labour (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998; Lazaridis & Poyago-Theotoki, 1999; Hatziprokopiou, 2006; Kandylis, 2006). In the early 2000s, migrants from the Middle East, Africa, and Asia, began arriving, often aiming to transit through Greece to other European countries, highlighting its role as both a destination and a transit country. The post-2008 debt crisis brought recession and austerity, unemployment and rising inequalities, and instability in migrants' legal status. In parallel, a significant number of established migrants left Greece or followed circular migration trajectories.

The early 2010s were characterised by a dominant xenophobic discourse and policies of border securitisation. In 2015, Greece became one of the main entry points to Europe for nearly one million newcomers from Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, and other countries, in what was portrayed as a 'refugee crisis'. Considered as a temporary and transit movement it brought a short-term alteration of the aforementioned negative stances. Nevertheless, after the closure of the Western Balkan Route, the implementation of the EU Hotspot approach, and the EU-Turkey Statement, many asylum seekers were obliged to stay in Greece for indefinite periods (Tramountanis, 2023). Applying for asylum became the main 'corridor' of regularisation, albeit with exceptions, in a context lacking integration opportunities, a fact that led many (recognised) refugees to move further. At the same time, recent legal developments on the acquisition of residence permits reveal how the immigration framework in Greece, still reproduces a regime of migrants' irregularisation (Papatzani et al., 2024).

3.2 Historical overview of the social, economic and /or political conditions and/or incidents that led to development of RMIs in Greece

The notion of 'multifaceted labyrinth' through which Tsitselikis (2019) characterised the complex asylum system after 2015 in Greece, is also characteristic of the entire immigration regime, including the governance of returns and the development of Return Migration Infrastructures.

During the 1990s, mass deportations to Albania were taking place every year, on the fringes (or in violation) of official legal rules (Baldwin-Edwards & Fakiolas, 1998), often as a result of the infamous 'sweep operations' performed by the police as a means to combat irregular migration and the allegedly associated criminality (Pavlou, 2009; Baldwin-Edwards, 2014).

By the mid-2000s, the enforcement of the Dublin II regulation contributed to the significant increase of the number of people trapped in Greece. During the debt/austerity period of the 2010s, worsening life conditions were exploited to augment racist discourses and discrimination against migrants as well as to implement stricter migration policies. These included, first, the securitisation of borders through the adoption of the 'Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration' in 2011, which included the construction of the Evros fence in the northeast borders of Greece, described as a 'technical

barrier' that would combat 'illegal' migration (Ministry of Citizen Protection, 2011). Second, the police 'sweep operation' 'Xenios Zeus' during 2012-'13, which was launched in urban centers and which through violent patrols and raids aimed at arresting and deporting irregular migrants (Pavlou, 2009; Karamanidou, 2016). As it was documented, this violent and racialised operation resulted in human rights violations and in increasing the number of people detained rather than identifying irregular migrants (HRW, 2012; 2013).

Moreover, during the same period, Frontex started being present in the country operating at the land (Evros) and sea (Aegean) borders; the IOM launched the AVR program; and a system of Pre-Removal Detention Centres (PRDCs) was established, regulating already existing detention facilities. In 2011 the Return Directive 2008/115/EC was transposed into Greek legislation (Law 3907/2011) to determine the operation of returns, without replacing Law 3386/2005 concerning administrative expulsion procedures (deportations). The coexistence of the two Laws leads to ambiguity and complexity, while Law 4825/2021 targeting to clarify their scope has not managed to overcome inconsistencies (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024).

As a reaction to 2015 refugee movement, the EU-Turkey Statement, as a de facto return agreement, stated that migrants and asylum seekers with unfounded or inadmissible claims would be 'returned' from Greece to Turkey. While its implementation resulted in a decrease in departures from Turkey, it did not increase the number of actual returns⁴. Moreover, since 2019-2020 a significant increase has been reported in the number of pushbacks at land and sea borders (BVMN, 2020a; Greek Ombudsman, 2023), turning them into a 'de facto general policy' (United Nations, General Assembly, 2022), despite Greek governments' arguments that these allegations 'are clearly unfounded' (Ministry of Migration and Asylum, 2021).

It should be also mentioned that further institutionalisation of returns was observed with the establishment of the Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals in 2020 and the position of a National Coordinator of Returns in late 2023 within the MMA. Moreover, the 'Joint Reintegration Services' (JRS) program was launched in August 2023, funded by Frontex, with Frontex return counsellors informing potential returnees in PRDCs about the program and its provisions, as mentioned by a key informant of the present research (GRstakeholder16_2023).

3.3 Return migration: trends and figures

According to Eurostat data, the number of third-country nationals (TCNs) 'found to be illegally present' in Greece ranged from approximately 40,000 to slightly over 100,000 for most of the period from 2008 to 2023, with one notable exception in 2015-2016. The number of TCNs ordered to leave showed a sharp increase after 2015 and then a decline over 2020-'23, with an exception in 2022. The number of those who actually returned following a return order represents a steady minority among those receiving such an order (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). The main nationalities of those receiving a return decision are Albania (17%), Pakistan (17%), Syria (12%), Afghanistan (10%), and Iraq (8%). Concerning migrants who did 'return' to another country during the same period, either by a forced return operation, an assisted 'voluntary' return operation, or a non-assisted one, the main countries of citizenship include Albania (51%), Pakistan (11%), Georgia (10%), and Iraq (7%).

⁴ Until its suspension by Turkey in 2020, the implementation of the Statement led to the return of 2,140 individuals. According to UNHCR data, sea arrivals to Greece decreased from about 800,000 in 2015 to about 173,000 in 2016 and less than 30,000 in 2017 (Ovacik et al., 2024).

Table 1. Numbers and percentages of TCNs ordered to leave, found to be illegally present, and returned following an order to leave. Source: Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024, authors' elaboration on Eurostat data.

Year	# TCNs ordered to leave	% in TCNs found to be illegally present	# TCNs returned following an order to leave (annual data)	% in the total # of TCNs ordered to leave
2015	104,575	11.5	14,390	13.8
2016	33,790	16.5	19,055	56.4
2017	45,765	67.2	18,060	39.5
2018	58,325	62.5	12,465	21.4
2019	78,880	64.1	9,650	12.2
2020	38,540	81.5	6,950	18.0
2021	28,815	75.8	6,855	23.8
2022	33,500	68.3	6,985	20.9

An overall decline in the number of returns is observed as shown in Figure 1; from over 19,000 in 2016-‘17, they dropped to about just above 7,000 in 2021-‘22. Forced returns as a share of the total have also declined, while voluntary returns have increased. The proportion of forced returns was reduced, since from 68-70% of total returns in 2016-‘17, they came to form 47.7% in 2021 and 38.2% in 2022. Assisted ‘voluntary’⁵ return through the IOM’s AVRR program appears to have proportionally increased (e.g. over 40% of total returns in the last couple of years as compared to about 30% in 2016-‘17), yet the number of beneficiaries in 2022 was 3,065, about half that in 2016, and far lower than in the early years of the program (more than 9,320 migrants participated in 2013, over 7,350 in 2014) (IOM, 2024c: 5).

⁵ ‘Voluntary’ return is depicted in two categories, the assisted and the non-assisted. As regards the latter, it was recorded in 2019, labelled (non-assisted) ‘voluntary’ (‘ουκιοθελής’ in Greek), which remains fairly low but is on the rise (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). In 2016 and early 2017 data, this appeared to refer to ‘voluntary’ returns implemented by the Police; but in the 2019-20 datasets is specified as ‘returns in the context of the returns directive [...] following a return order with a deadline for voluntary departure, holders of a 78α certificate (of non-removal for humanitarian reasons), withdrawal from an asylum claim’.

Figure 1. The development of different return types in Greece from 2016-2023 (*2023 data cover January to November). Source: Hatziprokopiou et al. 2024, authors' elaboration on data of the Greek Ministry of Civil Protection⁶.

Finally, as regards pushbacks, relevant estimations based on evidence and testimonies are provided by investigations and documentation by journalists and many human rights organisations. The recently established Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns has recorded a total number of alleged victims of at least 2,157 people from April 2020 to October 2022 (GNCHR, 2023), and a minimum number of 1,438 alleged victims between January 2022 and December 2023 from countries whose nationals are granted international protection status in Greece and the rest of the EU at significant rates (GNCHR, 2024).

Table 2. Numbers of alleged victims of pushbacks, based on the GNCHR Recording Mechanism of Informal Forced Returns. Source: GNCHR, 2023; 2024.

	April 2020 to October 2022	January 2022 to December 2023
Number of pushbacks alleged victims (at least)	2,157	1,438

⁶ Monthly data for 2016-19 are downloaded and elaborated from the government data repository (<https://archive.data.gov.gr/dataset/anagkastikes-kai-e8eloyisies-apelaseis-mh-nomimwn-metanastwn>, also available on the portal for European data), while 2020-2023 data come from the monthly statistic reports on Ministry of Migration & Asylum's website (<https://migration.gov.gr/en/statistika>).

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in Greece

In the following, the three Return Migration Infrastructures in Greece are discussed, particularly the assisted voluntary return, the forced removal, and the pushbacks, on the basis of their main actors, the mode of implementation ('doings'), and the materials and technologies. The flow maps presented also aim to provide an overview of each RMI.

4.1 Assisted Voluntary return

The major actor implementing AVRR programs in EU member states (and globally) is the International Organization for Migration (IOM). In Greece, IOM is actually the only actor implementing AVRR: it has provided assisted voluntary return programs since 2010, while reintegration measures were first introduced in 2012. In fact, AVRR was IOM's major activity in the country until 2015, when its role was significantly upgraded in supporting Greek authorities in various aspects of migration management (IOM, 2019b). The current program started in September 2023 and runs until the end of 2027.

In the past decade, IOM Greece implemented 'one of the largest AVRR operations' in the EU (IOM, 2019b: iii). Eurostat data confirm that this remains so in recent years, despite the drops in overall numbers: in 2021 and 2022 Greece came only second to Sweden in numbers of migrants returned via AVRR, and third in 2023, while annual returns from Greece make up 15.5-17% of total AVRRs in the EU⁷. In 2023, 2,705 migrants returned with AVRR, making up 42.7% of total returns (IOM, 2024b). The current program aims to return 17,000 individuals in a period of 52 months, to elaborate 1,700 reintegration plans and to provide accommodation for 1,700 individuals in OCAVRR. In accordance with the program's budget allocation, not all 'return beneficiaries' receive reintegration assistance: this was the case for just over 26% of 16,224 returnees between June 2016 - May 2019 and a similar proportion of 10,574 migrants who returned between September 2019 - July 2023; the vast majority, about 83%, received in-kind assistance to start a small business (IOM 2019b; 2023).

AVRR is officially addressed to 'migrants unable or unwilling to remain in the host country or country of transit and who decide to return to their country of origin' (IOM, 2024b), which includes various categories of migrants: migrants who have the right to stay, migrants who wait for a decision, or migrants who are irregularised. Moreover, the program gives 'special care and priority' to 'beneficiaries in a situation of vulnerability'⁸: the latter counted for 8% of total beneficiaries of the 2016-'23 program (nearly 70% on medical grounds), but increased to over 18% among returnees during 2019-'23. Returnees of the 2019-'23 program were in their majority nationals of Georgia (37%), Pakistan (23%) and Iraq (13%) - a composition somewhat less diverse compared to 2016-19, when the principal origin countries were Pakistan (26.3%), Iraq (25%), Georgia (12%), Afghanistan (8%) and Algeria (8%). But not all origin countries are considered for return: at present no returns to Albania and North Macedonia are implemented, neither to Syria, nor any longer to Ukraine, Afghanistan and Sudan. The countries that are in full or partial returns suspension are included in a constantly updated 'suspension list'⁹.

⁷ Eurostat Data: Third-country nationals returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data [migr_eirtn1__custom_13890092]

⁸ See AVRR description on IOM Greece website: <https://rb.gy/zcfopb>. Accessed 05/06/2025.

⁹ The suspension of assisted voluntary returns to certain countries or regions due to security concerns or operational challenges is part of the implementation of the principle of safety (see IOM, 2018).

Flow Chart 1. Flow Chart of the AVRR RMI in Greece

Map 1. The RMI of AVRR in metropolitan Athens

Actors

While IOM Greece is the AVRR major actor, it is not the only one. It cooperates with IOM Geneva and other IOM missions in countries of return, liaises with the embassies of these countries, collaborates with other international organizations (e.g. the UNHCR), negotiates with private companies (e.g. airlines), and networks with several NGOs (especially legal and medical ones). What is more, different units and departments within IOM Greece are involved in different aspects of implementation, including information and outreach, registration, movement operations, protection, medical screening, reintegration, and the operation of the OCAVRR. Greek authorities and governmental agencies, especially the MMA and, in particular, the Directorate for Returns and Withdrawals, the Asylum Service, and the Reception and Identification Service (RIS) - also involved in the management of the OCAVRR - as well as the Hellenic Police, among others, are naturally IOM's closest partners. Moreover, for the operation of the OCAVRR, IOM contracts private companies for catering, security and cleaning services. Hence, AVRR involves a complex network of actors operating at multiple scales (local, national, transnational), including institutional bodies and civil society organisations, their staff members, but also public and private services that are not organic components of the program (e.g. Greek public hospitals and social services, or airport authorities), as well as migrant communities and the returning migrants themselves.

Doings

The AVRR is presented as a linear process although it supposedly applies a case-by-case approach; thus, in practice, it may not unfold through straightforward and sequential

procedures. Migrants who have decided to take the return path contact IOM (via physical presence, by phone, or online) to arrange an appointment. They may have learned about the program from IOM's outreach activities across the country, which include street work and visits e.g. to reception or detention centres, but also information campaigns involving outdoors and digital advertisement. Registration takes place usually at IOM headquarters in Athens, although it is possible to register at remote locations (e.g. Hotspots on the east Aegean islands) via the Outreach department. In order to be able to register, migrants need to submit a return order issued by the Police Department of Aliens, which they may need to arrange, depending on their legal status, after referral from the IOM. Once registered, they may continue to stay at their previous residence, whether a private apartment, reception centre or detention facility, unless they are found to be in a situation of vulnerability in which case they are eligible for accommodation at the OCAVRR. In the meantime, they may be involved in several consultation sessions, including medical screening, assessing their family situation and potential risks upon return, as well as reintegration planning for those eligible. Beneficiaries are then assisted with travel arrangements: from the issuing of travel documents and entry requirements to booking flight tickets (or even organizing charter flights in exceptional cases), arranging transport, and escorting returnees to the airport.

Materials and technologies

The AVRR involves a complex set of materialities and spatialities, some obvious and visible yet others not so much, as well as various technologies. A number of different places and localities form part of the AVRR infrastructure making up a multileveled and diverse geography. These include the IOM headquarters in Athens, a regional office in Thessaloniki, and presence in five towns of mainland Greece, Crete and the five 'hotspot' islands of the east Aegean. Police departments, reception centres, detention facilities, Asylum Service offices and the premises of various NGOs may also be places where potential returnees may be found at various encounters with or stages of the program, as described above. Registered migrants who are considered vulnerable and have nowhere to stay may be offered accommodation at the OCAVRR, located at Galatsi at the northern border of Athens municipality. The Airport itself becomes occasionally part of the AVRR. Some procedures take place in virtual space, making use of a range of digital technologies. These include an Online Scheduling Appointment (OSA) platform, or the Migrant Management Operational System Application (MiMOSA) whereby AVRR participants' data are stored, as well as data from a set of monitoring surveys conducted by IOM, among others. Materials include a host of things, such as cameras, uniforms, vehicles and various types of documents. The campaigning toolbox includes multi-language leaflets informing on the program and OCAVRR, promotion videos and other online material available on the IOM Greece website and social media platforms, advertisement panels e.g. on bus stations and other parts of Athens, etc. The IOM logo is omnipresent in the above, appearing also on the plastic bag that returnees need to carry at the airport to be identifiable and store their documents.

By examining the interplay of these actors, their roles and relations, the doings and procedures, and the materials and technologies, we can gain a deeper understanding of the AVRR program as a complex and dynamic RMI. This is done in chapter 5, drawing on GAPs WP3 fieldwork research.

4.2 Forced Removal

Forced removals in Greece are based on two different legal frameworks and their parallel implementation results in a highly complex legal system (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). In 2023, 29,869 removal orders were issued by the Hellenic Police (in comparison with roughly 30,600 in 2022 and 21,000 in 2021): about two out of three returns were based on Law 3907/2011 (transposing the Return Directive), and one out of three were based on Law 3386/2005 (on administrative expulsions), in derogation from the Return Directive (RSA, 2024).

Actors

In terms of actors, the whole system consists of three basic groups, though some confusion of competencies and lack of coordination often emerge (Grstakeholder6_2023). The first group consists of the national governmental and supranational agencies that coordinate and monitor returns. Government actors include the agencies of two Ministries of the Greek government, i.e. the Ministry of Migration and Asylum (MMA) and the Ministry for Citizen Protection (MCP) – the former reflecting the need for migration governance in terms of legal regulation and integration and the latter illustrating the management of migration specifically as an issue of public order and security. Along with being responsible for decision making at the higher political level, the two Ministries have developed specific departments that specialize on returns in terms of bureaucratic management, either indirectly (as with the National Coordinating Centre for Border Control and Surveillance of the MCP) or directly (as with the Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals and the National Coordinator of Returns, both belonging to the MMA). At the European level, the role of AMIF is of key importance, since it serves as the funding mechanism for activities as diverse as the management of accommodation facilities and the external monitoring of returns by the Greek Ombudsman. At a higher level, the European approach is coordinated by the EU Return Coordinator and the High-Level Network for Returns.

The second group consists of those bodies that are responsible for implementing the procedures of forced returns on the ground, the key actor here being the Hellenic Police. While operational duties are shared by various sectoral and regional departments, the organogram of the Hellenic Police includes a devoted 'branch' of Foreigners and Border Protection. Importantly, apart from their responsibility to arrest and identify foreign citizens irregularly present in the country, police authorities issue return/expulsion decisions and run the detention facilities. Within these facilities, one should also notice the presence of AEMY, a pre-existing public Limited Company (S.A.) specializing in the management of health units, which expanded its initial activities in 2017 to undertake the provision of health services and psychosocial support in the PRDCs¹⁰. Private companies also undertake service provision, as in the case of distribution of meals and security services. Two governmental agencies of the MMA, i.e. the Asylum Service and the Appeals Authority also play an indirect important role in implementation, with their authority in issuing return decisions after the rejection of asylum claims. Last but not least, at the supranational level there is Frontex which, beyond supporting the national authorities with border control (including prevention and detection), is a key actor in coordinating return operations by flight. Frontex deploys Standing Corps officers in Greece.

¹⁰ After its termination in the end of 2023, the initial period of AEMY's involvement in PRDCs was extended until 2029 (<https://tamey.gov.gr/amif2021-2027/calls/grant-agreements/6007062/>).

Flow Chart 2. Flow Chart of the forced removal RMI in Greece.

monitoring of the entire system. The (territorial) administrative courts receive and judge on appeals against return/expulsion orders and against detention orders. The Greek Ombudsman, as the official mechanism for external monitoring oversees human rights issues and publishes an annual report with their findings and suggestions (e.g. Greek Ombudsman, 2023). At the same time, various NGOs and civil society organisations review and criticize various aspects of the operation of the whole infrastructure. A similar duty is undertaken by the European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CPT) as a specialised independent monitoring body of the Council of Europe.

Doings

The forced removals infrastructure is organised along a seemingly linear procedure that starts with the identification of a non-Greek national who has no right to stay in the country (or has been convicted for certain categories of law violation or even is considered dangerous for public order or public health) and ends with their final removal from the country. In practice, the whole infrastructure is much more complicated and includes multiple steps, different temporalities, cul-de-sacs, and points of exit.

Obviously, national borders are a key entry point in the infrastructure since, with their control mechanisms and procedures, they aim to detect those who arrive and categorize them through a process of identification and screening. However, detection can also take place very far from the borders and long after border crossing. Importantly, detention also involves migrants whose legal status has been terminated for various reasons, even if they have never violated the legal procedures for border crossing. Moreover, particularly on the border islands, expulsion decisions are issued pre-emptively against TCNs entering Greece, before their identification, even if they subsequently apply for international protection and obtain a permit to stay in the country (GRstakeholder6_2023).

One's detection for purposes of identification is followed by multiple procedures of legal examination which cannot be summarised here but basically consist of procedures having to do with asylum claims and procedures having to do with residence and work permits. Whenever a claim for international protection or any other legal status is rejected, the responsible authorities issue a return order, and then applicants can either be detained or left at liberty with an obligation to leave the country. When detained, the purpose is that they end up in a forced return operation, organised by the Greek authorities alone or in collaboration with Frontex.

Detention is a key aspect of the forced removal infrastructure as it is the rule rather than the exception whenever a return or expulsion decision is issued. Apart from the reasons for detentions prescribed in the Return Directive (i.e. the risk of absconding or a migrant avoiding or hampering the return process), as the Greek Ombudsman has observed (2019), detention decisions are very often based on public security and public order reasons, pertaining to sentences for the possession of forged documents or non-possession of documents. As a result, third country nationals often end up in detention for the sole reason of entering the country.

In 2023 alone, the Hellenic Police issued more than 24,000 detention orders, 10,000 under Law 3907/2011, roughly the same number under Law 3386/2005 and 3,600 in the asylum process (RSA, 2024). Various forms of deprivation of liberty may occur even before a return/expulsion decision, as for example immediately after the border crossing, highlighting the multiple temporalities and inconsistencies of the procedure (GRstakeholder6_2023). Indeed, all newcomers are held in what can be described as 'early' detention in the Reception

and Identification Centres (RICs) for a period of 25 days, solely for the purpose of identification. Prolonged detention is also observed, since migrants may be detained for long periods in the Pre-Removal Detention Centres (PRDCs) after a return decision has been issued; periods that reportedly exceed 12 months or even when their deportation is not feasible.

Detainees are not informed in advance about their return but usually only one or two days earlier (GRstakeholder12_2024). Moreover, the police frequently transfer detainees to the Airport Police Station as ‘alternates’. This means that in case some of the returnees assigned to a specific return operation are exempted from the procedure (for example due to unexpected health conditions or due to last minute legal issues), then those ‘alternates’ replace them and are forcibly returned. If not returned, these individuals have to spend the night at the airport before being transferred to the place of detention again (basically to the detention centre of Amygdaleza in Athens) (GRstakeholder8_2023).

In what concerns the operation of the transfers by land and by air, the Greek Ombudsman (2019; 2022; 2023; 2024) has sporadically documented certain issues and shortcomings that violate the returnees’ rights and dignity. These include absence of interpreters and absence of fit-to-travel certificates.

Materials and Technologies

The material world of the forced return infrastructure can be summarised in three broad and interrelated categories. The first corresponds to the mechanisms of surveillance and detection either at the borders or inside the national territory. It includes materials of practical and symbolic significance, such as cameras and drones and the infamous fence in the border region of Evros. The second has to do with monitoring and restricting the mobility of potential returnees. It includes the places of detention, namely the prison-like PRDCs¹¹ and various police stations around the country where migrants are detained in generally harsh and sometimes inhuman conditions (BVMN, 2023; GCR, 2024). In the seven operating PRDCs (of a total capacity of 3,676), these conditions include overcrowding, lack of medical personnel, lack of entertainment activities, and lack of sufficient hygiene and non-food items, including clothes and shoes, clean mattresses and clean blankets. The situation in the police stations is even more devastating for the detainees, with no outdoor access, lack of sufficient natural light and insufficient food. Finally, the third category includes all those materials and places (such as police vans, aircrafts and the Athens airport) that are directly connected with the enforcement of the removal. Despite certain improvements (Greek Ombudsman, 2023; 2024), the material conditions here include returnees being transferred locked-up in vans with confinement department and long-lasting waiting in uncomfortable conditions.

In parallel with these materials, various technologies are used in every step for purposes of data collection and storage. They include technological tools shared by various actors, as for recording individual data with fingerprinting, nationality assessment, age assessment, and medical screening, e.g. the Alkyoni II database of the GAS for the identification of (rejected) asylum applicants and potential returnees also accessed by the Police. The National List of Undesirable Aliens, also connected with the Schengen Information System (SIS), is an example of the outcomes of such technologies. The Hellenic Police operates a specialised application called ‘Foreigners’ Circulation Mapping’ which is being upgraded at the moment, in accordance

¹¹ Seven PRDCs were active in 2023, two of which in Athens, one in the nearby city of Corinth, three in the border Region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace and one in the island of Kos. Two were in suspension (in Lesbos and Samos). See GCR, 2024.

with the RECAMAS reference model developed by Frontex. The upgrading has been funded by AMIF and Internal Security Fund (IFS)¹².

4.3 Pushbacks

Pushbacks from Greece have been a well-known practice for over three decades (Karamanidou and Kasperek, 2022; GNCHR, 2023; 2024). Pushback at the Greek – Turkish land borders started to be documented in mid-2000s (Amnesty International, 2005; Pro Asyl, 2007; HRW, 2008), while pushbacks at the Aegean border since 2009 as migration sea routes diverted to the east Mediterranean. Most pushbacks from Greece are directed towards Turkey with the majority of them occurring at the East Aegean borders (mostly near the islands of Lesbos, Samos, Chios, Leros, Rhodes, Kos) and at Evros land/river border. However, pushbacks have been also reported from Crete (Schauseil, 2022) and from the mainland. Moreover, other practices taking the form of pushforwards or non-rescue have been also noted, as was the case of the infamous Pylos shipwreck from Peloponnese.

Actors

The main actors involved in the acts of pushbacks are primarily the Hellenic Police and the Hellenic Coastguard (Greek Ombudsman, 2021; 2023; GNCHR, 2023; 2024). The presence of Frontex personnel has also been noted leading to investigations concerning its practices (BVMN, 2020a; Karamanidou and Kasperek, 2020). Moreover, the role of balaclava-clad, black uniformed and/or paramilitary is commonly attested (Pro Asyl, 2013; Amnesty International, 2014; 2021; ARSIS et al., 2018; Greek Ombudsman, 2021). In the past years, reports pinpoint to the involvement of other migrants who are either coerced in doing so (Chondrogiannos, 2022; Lighthouse reports, 2022) or play a more active role (i.e. as translators, ‘commandos’, etc.) in direct contact with the Hellenic Police. Since cars and vans are involved in the pushbacks, their drivers (officers or civilians) are also involved. The Greek state denies its involvement in pushbacks, albeit the sheer number of reports makes the Greek state complicit in violations ingrained in pushbacks and in their normalisation as practice.

Doings

Pushbacks commonly take the form of apprehension of border-crossers from reaching Greek territory. In all cases, pushbacks entail violent practices that violate all aspects of human, refugee and humanitarian law. Besides endangering migrants by forcing them to cross dangerous waters and territories, during the process of being pushed back, there are plenty and substantial allegations of migrants been beaten (by security forces and balaclava-clad men), subjected to degrading and/or inhuman or even torturous treatment, harassed, terrorised, stripped off their clothes, subjected to water and food deprivation for prolonged

¹² See the details on the devoted web page of MMA: [tamey.gov.gr/amif2021-2027/calls/grant-agreements/6016624/]

Flow Chart 3. Flow Chart of the pushbacks RMI in Greece.

periods of time, and having their properties stolen and/or destroyed (Amnesty International, 2014; ARSIS et al., 2018; BVMN 2020b; 2021; Greek Ombudsman, 2021; 2023; GNCHR, 2023; 2024). Additionally, as will be detailed further on, pushbacks commonly entail abductions and illegal detention of migrants.

Sea pushbacks often take place either through wave creation from navy or coastguard boats in order to push the incoming boat further from Greek waters; or through towing the incoming boats towards Turkish waters or through not rescuing distressed boats and leaving them adrift in the sea (ECRE, 2024). However, they also take place after migrants have disembarked and are on their way to a village or to filing an asylum claim. In these cases, people are initially detected, arrested (by security forces and/or balaclava-clad men) and detained at an undefined facility. They are then transferred (via vehicles and balaclava-clad men) to the shores, put into dingies or even life rafts and pushed to the open sea. Besides the aforementioned violence, numerous recent reports testify that people have been pushed to the sea with their hands strapped (Smith and Steele, 2024).

Reports argue that the highest number of land pushbacks takes place at the Evros river border, either upon arrival on Greek territory or from further inland (even from villages in the area). As in the sea/island pushbacks, testimonies also refer to practices of detection (by security forces and/or balaclava-clad men), apprehensions and abductions of migrants (by force or by false promises) who are en route, in villages or even from official detention centres (Greek Ombudsman, 2021; 2023; GNCHR, 2023; 2024). Migrants are then driven to unidentified facility, detained and then driven back to Evros river where they are forced to cross it through dingies or even by swimming (ARSIS et al., 2018; BVMN, 2020b). The aforementioned violent practices are employed also in land pushbacks. Land pushbacks have also been reported from the mainland, concerning people who were intending to file an asylum claim, but also people with international protection or other legal documentation (Karamanidou and Kasperek, 2020). In particular, migrants have been removed by police vans from facilities halfway across the territory, such as the refugee camp in Diavata and the Drama Paranesti PRDC (Statewatch, 2020).

Materials and Technologies

A range of security and surveillance technologies including radars, thermal cameras, drones, thermovision vans, the automated border surveillance centre, five operational centres and the coordination centre at Nea Vyssa (several of them funded by EU funds) as well as Evros fence (2012) and its 2020 extension (not funded by the EU) constitute Evros' security assemblage. These are complemented by army technologies and infrastructures (i.e. army vehicles, weapons, further surveillance and communication technologies and the military infrastructure that manages the border, including military bases and buildings, personnel working in them, contractors, etc.). Similar security and surveillance technologies and military infrastructures constitute the respective assemblage in the islands, which is enhanced by nautical equipment and technologies operated by the navy, the coastguard and Frontex. Finally, these are complemented by police's materialities, including border police stations and detentions centres, police cars and motorbikes as well as policing armour. Weapons and immobilising devices, uniforms and masks are essential for all army/security bodies as well as for the paramilitary. One should also account for the unofficial sites used for detention/kidnapping, as well as for the unidentified vehicles and the mobile phones and communication applications used (Pro Asyl, 2013; Karamanidou and Kasperek, 2020). Lastly, funding –be it national, EU

or other– is crucial in acquiring the necessary technologies and paying for the personnel and the consultants. While not officially addressed to such activities, funds from EU Security Fund, the EU Integrated Border Management Fund and AMIF are used for the purchase of equipment and technologies that are eventually used in pushback operations. Furthermore, research funding also contributed to the development of technologies regarding border management.

In terms of resisting and reporting pushbacks, appeals to the European Court of Justice for an injunction (GRstakeholder13_2024), mobile phones, social media and communications applications are the main means of doing so. Reporters, NGO workers, GIS experts and lawyers are the primary actors assisting victims of pushbacks and using their knowledge and technologies for support.

Overall, pushbacks are nowadays characterised by an organised, systematic, and operational character (GNCHR, 2024; GRstakeholder11_2024). The particular operational features that demand cooperation among actors, the operational means that depend on specific materials and geographies, a ‘modus operandi’ built up as ‘a progression of stages’ (GNCHR, 2024) and the division of labour among actors (GNCHR, 2024; GRstakeholder11_2024), permit us to argue about *the infrastructuralisation of pushbacks* in Greece.

5. Case study: The RMI of the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) in Greece

This section discusses the Return Migration Infrastructure (RMI) of the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program in Greece which was selected as a case study of the original qualitative research in the country. The analysis focuses on i) the actors involved, ii) their ‘doings’ and implementation steps, iii) the materials and technologies shaping the RMI, iv) the relations (both collaborations and tensions) between actors, materials, and technologies as well as several emerging issues and implementation gaps.

5.1 Actors involved in AVRR and their role

As sketched in section 4.1, a large number of actors are engaged in AVRR in Greece, as shown in the box below. As an international organisation specialising (among other issues) in assisted return migration, IOM maintains a crucial role, as the project contractor and leading actor, responsible for the everyday operation of the program. Other actors play multiple roles and add complexity with their responsibilities and initiatives at the local, national, and transnational level.

Box 1. Actors involved in AVRR in Greece

- Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals (MMA)
- Greek Asylum Service (MMA)
- Reception and Identification Service (MMA)
- Service for the Management of European and Development Programs (MCP)
- The Hellenic Police (MCP)
- International Organization for Migration (Information Outreach Department, Registration Department, Movement Operation Department, Protection Department, Medical Department, Reintegration Department, OCAVRR staff, interpreters, cultural mediators, social workers, psychologists, doctor, nurses)
- IOM Geneva, IOM in transit and origin countries
- Ministries of Foreign Affairs of return countries (e.g. MoFA Pakistan)
- Embassies and consulates in Greece and abroad
- Public hospitals, public hospitals’ social services, private clinic, Organisation against drugs (OKANA)
- National Centre for Social Solidarity, Shelters for Unaccompanied Minors
- The Health Units Limited Company (S.A.) (AEMY) operating in PRDCs
- NGOs on medical issues (Medecins du Monde, BABEL Day Centre, Médecins Sans Frontières, PRAXIS, MOSAIC, Social Pharmacy of the Medical Association)
- NGOs on legal issues (Greek Council for Refugees, Human Rights 360)
- Municipal authorities
- The Authorities of Athens International Airport (Security office)
- Airlines
- Private companies, e.g. in OCAVRR (security company, cleaning company, catering company), in airports in transit countries (through vouchers for launch in case of long waiting)
- Private lawyers
- Migrants’ communities

- Potential returnees¹³

The MMA (Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals, established in 2020) is the main authority responsible for migrants' returns at the national scale. From August 2023 until the end of 2027, MMA will subsidize AVRR; earlier it was the Ministry of Citizen Protection (MCP). The Greek Asylum Service of the MMA is also an important collaborating actor as regards the legal status procedures of returnees. The Reception and Identification Service (RIS) of MMA is the managing authority of the Open Centre for migrants registered for Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (OCAVRR), in cooperation with other actors, with a staff of approximately seven people. The Hellenic Police is involved in different steps of AVRR with a multifold role, albeit to a lesser extent in comparison to forced removals.

The predominant role and the activities of IOM are operationalised through multiple branches, departments, and staff roles, including:

- i. the Information Outreach Department that coordinates the network of regional employees, the outreach assistants, who visit different facilities all over Greece to inform migrants of different statuses and periods of arrival in the country about AVRR and to identify potential applicants. By the time of the research, the personnel included thirteen people for the periphery of the country and seven for Athens (GRstakeholder2_2023);
- ii. the Registration Department in IOM's headquarters in Athens consisting of six people, of which five caseworkers and one team leader;
- iii. the Operation Department, consisting of four people, including Operation Escorts who assist in the airport during the return procedures. They are a liaison both with other IOM Departments and external collaborating actors at multiple scales (such as the embassies and consulates, the police, airport security, travel agencies, origin and transit countries, etc.);
- iv. the Protection Department, consisting of five people based at the IOM's headquarters and four more based at the OCAVRR, mainly psychologists and social workers;
- v. the Medical Department that ensures that the the returnees are 'fit-to-travel' and takes care of medical issues of the AVRR's and OCAVRR's participants;
- vi. the Reintegration Department which was launched in 2012 and targets the most vulnerable AVRR participants. Today it consists of a staff of three people, significantly reduced if compared with the previous years (GRstakeholder5_2023).

Furthermore, for the daily operation of OCAVRR, the RIS, IOM (with the 'focal point', a medical team, interpreters, and other staff roles), and private companies provide personnel. Regarding private companies, these include a security company that provides services on a 24-hour basis, a cleaning company, and a catering company for offering meals for both adults and children. This provision of services from private actors in assisted voluntary returns is reminiscent of the privatisation and outsourcing of services related to pre-removal detention in many European countries (Oomkens and Kalir, 2020).

Several other actors are also involved, including over 54 embassies and consulates of third countries in Greece and abroad (IOM, 2023) for the identification of migrants, the validation of passports, and the issuing of travel documents, the Authorities of the Athens International Airport (concerning passport controls, security provision, etc.), airlines, and several NGOs

¹³ Returnees' agency is considered a significant part of the notion of Return Migration Infrastructures in GAPs project. However, their experiences, practices and perceptions are discussed in the WP7 Country Dossier of Greece (see Papatzani et al., 2025).

related to medical and legal services provision (see Box 1). Interestingly, while a range of civil society actors and independent authorities are engaged in the monitoring and advocacy of issues related to RMIs of forced returns and pushbacks in Greece, AVRR does not seem to attract the interest of human rights or other advocacy NGOs, possibly due to the voluntary initiation of the process. Migrants' organised communities and their networks complete the puzzle of actors as they often inform their members about AVRR.

5.2 Implementation / 'doings' of AVRR

The implementation of AVRR is characterised by complexity rather than a (perceived) linearity. Acknowledging this, the analysis of this section follows a linear description by simultaneously highlighting the different versions of the procedure that emerge for migrant returnees.

5.2.1 Outreach

The information outreach work concerns AVRR's communication practices with prospective applicants, aiming at informing migrant population about the existence of the AVRR program and the option of assisted voluntary return. As an IOM representative noted, returnees 'are fully informed about these procedures from the first step but again during the following steps [...]' (GRstakeholder1_2024). A devoted Department, through the outreach assistants, implements regular 'information visits' and street work 'at spaces/areas with a high concentration of migrants' (GRstakeholder2_2023). These activities target migrants found at the reception camps in mainland Greece, the Closed Controlled Access Centres (CCACs) and the Hotspots on the Aegean islands, PRDCs (e.g. Amygdaleza in Attica), Police stations, regional asylum offices, embassies, hospitals, migrants' communities, shops, and businesses, or other places where potential participants could be reached. Social media advertisements and information campaigns also form part of the outreach responsibilities. Additionally, the Department's mandate includes data collection on the effectiveness of the information campaigns.

The Department regularly collects information about new arrivals at the aforementioned facilities from respective authorities (the police authorities, camp managers, PRDCs' authorities, etc.), including detention facilities. Thus, part of information outreach takes place in detention facilities and refers to detainees who get informed about AVRR by IOM employees through their regular visits. Moreover, information outreach also takes place in spaces of asylum and protection, such as the reception camps mentioned above, highlighting the *intersections between (the infrastructures of) return and asylum* (see Section 5.3.1). The Outreach Department also registers migrants willing to participate in AVRR but are not able to visit IOM's headquarters in Athens, and is responsible for Protection issues in case AVRR participants reside far from Athens. Moreover, information about the program may reach migrants indirectly, e.g. from friends and acquaintances, through word of mouth, including from migrant communities.

5.2.2 Registration

Before registering in AVRR, migrants may be detained (in a detention center or a police department), may live in a reception and accommodation facility (e.g. in a camp while waiting

for a legal procedure to complete), or be irregularised anywhere in the country in private residence. Registration usually takes place at the IOM headquarters in Athens, but may also occur in remote places in Greece by a unit ('klimakio') of outreach assistants (GRstakeholder2_2023), including detention spaces. Implementing registration while in detention raises *questions about the voluntariness* of the procedure (see section 6.4.4).

Registration is implemented through the IOM MiMOSA database and is performed by registration assistants and interpreters or cultural mediators when requested by the applicants (GRstakeholder3_2023). Data and document verification through MiMOSA aims to *ensure* that the person concerned *has not already benefited* from AVRR in Greece or elsewhere in the past, a fact that would indicate a circular trajectory (as described in 6.4.4). If the person lacks any identification documents (e.g. passport), his/her identification is implemented through the respective embassy or consulate before issuing (temporary) travel documents. This procedure may take some time to be completed (GRstakeholder3_2023). The returnees are instructed to contact the consulate authorities on their own after their registration in AVRR. However, regular communication between the consulate authorities and IOM Greece facilitates the process.

Different steps are added to the procedure depending on the *legal status* of the applicants and whether a *return decision* has been issued. For example, in the case of an irregular migrant who has already received a return decision, IOM makes use of that decision to proceed with the rest of the process. In case an irregular migrant has not received a return decision, IOM provides him/her with a referral document and makes an appointment at the Aliens Directorate/Immigration Service (of the Hellenic Police) in Athens for fingerprinting and issuing an 'exit permit' interoffice memo, namely a return decision to be executed within approximately one month, necessary for the departure at the airport. The return decision is usually issued in four or five days; migrants receive it from the police and hand it to IOM (GRstakeholder1_2024).

If the applicant is an asylum seeker or a beneficiary of international protection, IOM informs him/her that he/she must *resign from the asylum application, the asylum status, and the respective rights*, an action that functions as a return decision. Before retracting their status, they are offered legal information on the consequences of this action, from NGOs such as the Greek Council for Refugees (GRstakeholder4_2023). IOM then provides them with a referral document and arranges an appointment at the GAS office in Alimos, close to the IOM headquarters (see 6.4.1) (GRstakeholder1_2024). *The obligation to retract from a secure legal status creates a phase in the procedure during which the returnee becomes irregular*. Thus, *irregularisation* becomes an *important symbolic part of the AVRR process*, even if it takes place shortly before the departure (Papatzani et al., 2024) (see 6.4.4). It is worth noticing that any retraction from previous legal status cannot be cancelled in case a person enrolled in AVRR finally decides not to leave.

[...] IOM advises to resign the rights just before departure [...] In exceptional cases of people with medical problems, the resignation can be done even at the airport e.g. they may need to have access to state health services, e.g. chemotherapy, until the last minute' (GRstakeholder3_2023).

After registration, migrants usually continue to stay where they did before (including in detention), apart from those who apply for accommodation to OCAVRR if they fulfil certain criteria. Registration to OCAVRR takes place in the same way as registration in AVRR. When arriving at OCAVRR the RIS informs participants about the regulations of the facility and

registers them in the OCAVRR database, from which the occupancy report is automatically provided daily (GRstakeholder9_2023).

5.2.3 Protection

The recently established Protection Department at IOM headquarters is responsible for the protection screening of the participants, including their ‘Risk Assessment’, ‘Rapid Vulnerability Assessment’, family tracing, and ‘Best Interest Assessment’ for unaccompanied minors, as well as confirming the existence of a supportive environment in the country of origin (GRstakeholder4_2023). All these procedures may take some time to be completed and may result in *different rhythms* of the whole process for the persons concerned.

For applicants residing in hotspots, if the geographical restriction is not lifted, the protection screening will be implemented on the island (GRstakeholder1_2024). Then, if no protection issue emerges, the police will transfer them to a detention center in broader Athens. As an IOM representative mentioned, ‘no ticket booking, no resigning an asylum claim, no fingerprint taking will proceed before an e-mail from the Protection Department is sent to Operation saying “OK, proceed”’ (GRstakeholder1_2024).

Another protection team from the same Department is based in OCAVRR and conducts in-depth examinations of OCAVRR participants regardless of existing vulnerabilities (GRstakeholder4_2023). The existence of OCAVRR, as a safe and intercultural environment (GRstakeholder1_2024) is considered extremely helpful for participants’ protection while in Greece, due to the social, medical, psycho-educational, recreational, and creative services and activities provided, as well as the material assistance of accommodation provision per se. For instance, victims of gender violence are often accommodated there.

On the other hand, being undocumented while participating in AVRR or OCAVRR may result in being detained¹⁴ if arrested, thus causing additional protection issues for participants. As with the case of registration procedures, protection continues for AVRR participants in remote places even if they are detained, through phone calls by the Outreach Assistants.

‘Yes, we cannot hide that there are cases in which some of our beneficiaries are free and then get detained. But this does not stop, this is the important thing, it does not stop the procedure. [...] our team will go to see her in Amygdaleza [...] Everything will be (properly) done. Either with a physical presence or on the phone’ (GRstakeholder1_2024).

Thus, instead of being mutually exclusive, *AVRR and detention are occasionally intertwined*. Participating in AVRR while in detention can be seen as an ambivalent condition, as discussed also in 5.4.4.

5.2.4 Medical procedures

The identification of the medical assistance needs takes place already during the registration of an AVRR applicant. In cases of several health issues and vulnerabilities, as well as in cases

¹⁴ As mentioned by an IOM representative, the proportion of detainees is variable but generally less than 10% (GRstakeholder1_2024).

of applicants over 62 years old, applicants are referred to the medical team (GRstakeholder1_2024), which monitors them until their return: 'We had some cases in which the people were in a stabilisation program for months' (GRstakeholder1_2024).

An important step is the medical team's 'fitness to travel' or '*fit-to-travel*' or 'fit with requirements' decision (e.g. a medical/operational escort, oxygen on the flight, wheelchair, etc.) taken by the IOM medical team. It ensures that even in cases of medical issues, the persons concerned can safely fly to their country (GRstakeholder1_2024). A common reason for not providing the 'fit-to-travel' is high blood pressure during the pre-embarkation check, as has happened often with female returnees from Georgia, who eventually travelled later (GRstakeholder1_2024).

Particularly for applicants who are to be accommodated in OCAVRR, an x-ray needs to be taken in advance. Yet, having this test in a public hospital might cause days of delay which could be harmful to people in urgent need of accommodation. In such cases, IOM arranges an appointment with a private clinic. IOM staff and OCAVRR managers may also adopt *informal practices and temporary 'exceptions'* from this requirement on a '*case-by-case basis*' to facilitate timely accommodation in the facility (GRstakeholder10_2024).

The most common medical issues in OCAVRR are psychiatric ones. As mentioned, the difficulties of the journey and the overall circumstances in Greece have played a role in motivating them to participate in AVRR (GRstakeholder10_2024; Papatzani et al., 2025). In OCAVRR there is also the possibility to isolate a patient when needed, something that started during the COVID-19 pandemic.

When medical check-ups have to be implemented in hospitals, IOM arranges the appointment when applicants possess a social insurance number. They are usually accompanied by an IOM interpreter, and in very serious cases by a nurse or the OCAVRR doctor, as 'they find it difficult to cope with the health system' (GRstakeholder10_2024).

A common phenomenon observed in Greece as well as across Europe is the *recent increase of AVRR participants facing medical issues and 'vulnerabilities'* (GRstakeholder10_2024). Currently, about 30-40% of AVRR participants have various medical issues (GRstakeholder10_2024). This could point to two possible factors affecting people's participation in AVRR: i) the impact of the deterioration of the national public health care system in Greece in relation to the precarity of the undocumented status and ii) the possibility of covering part of medical expenses in the return countries through the in-kind re-integration assistance.

5.2.5 Operation

The Operation Department is concerned with all the necessary steps for the returnees' travel arrangements: the issuance of identification documents from embassies and consulates; the issuance of travel documents or the check of existing ones; the booking of flights - usually commercial except for charter for large numbers of returnees from the same country; the possible use of operational escort or medical escort; the hand-over and reception assistance with IOM offices for the transit flights if required and in the destination countries; the setup of departure groups in neighbouring countries by gathering returnees altogether; the arrangements of the pre-departure sessions two days before the flight, the medical pre-embarkation check (PEC) 24-72 hours before the flight, the information provision on flight details; the escorting of the returnees until their boarding at the airplane gate. The responsibility for such multiple tasks creates a feeling of personal commitment among the

employees of the Department. As one of them noted ‘we do not see the people at all, but we know them by heart!’ through the MiMOSA platform stages (GRstakeholder3_2023).

As regards travel documents, when there is not a valid passport, the embassies issue the so-called ‘*laissez-passer*’, a temporary travel document that is valid for 30 days and for the particular route to the country of return. If the respective embassy declines to identify the person as its national and refuses to issue the *laissez-passer*, then the return process is cancelled (GRstakeholder3_2023). The possession of travel and identification documents, thus, may result in *different rhythms* of the procedure for the people concerned.

The operation procedures also include the arrangements during the day of the flight, with the support of the IOM Airport office, the members of which are officially considered as airport staff and have access to the entire airport’s premises (GRstakeholder2_2023) and the Outreach Department staff. On the day of the flight, returnees at liberty arrive at the Airport’s departure meeting point on their own. For OCAVRR residents, when needed, the transfer takes place with an IOM van and a note from the returnee that he/she consents to enter the car (GRstakeholder2_2023). Those in detention are transported to the airport by police officers. IOM representatives mention that the police escort is discreet, with a conventional police vehicle and plainclothes officers. IOM representatives have requested that those transferred from detention centers should not wear handcuffs and this has been respected by the officers (GRstakeholder2_2023).

Large groups of returnees are checked in *en masse* and it is recommended that they all sit together either at the airport or on the plane. Returnees must carry their AVRR card (see 5.3.2), their passports, the ‘exit permit’ interoffice memo (return decision), and the bag with IOM insignia. They bring their documents with them, except if the travel documents have been handed directly from the consulate to IOM to cover the cost for those unable to do so; in that case, IOM personnel hand the documents to the migrants at the airport (GRstakeholder1_2024). During the cross-check/identification check and the stamping of passports/documents, there are cases of people for whom the system alerts about a possible warrant or other measure pending against them in their country, in which case their departure is cancelled. At the gate, the AVRR card will be handed over from the migrants to the IOM team and destroyed (for personal data protection reasons), while the interoffice memo will be stamped and collected by the airport police officer as proof that the migrant has boarded the plane (GRstakeholder2_2023). The financial assistance is handed over to the returnee at the airport from the IOM accounting team immediately after the identification check and before proceeding to the gate, in the presence of an airport security police officer (GRstakeholder3_2023). At the moment of the research, the financial aid for those residing on the Greek mainland was 1,000 euros, while for those residing on the Aegean islands, it was 500 euros¹⁵.

5.2.6 Reintegration

Returnees’ reception after arrival in the country of return includes provision for any medical issues existing. Then, reintegration follows, for those eligible, as the final step of the AVRR procedure that starts after a referral from the Protection Department. Reintegration assistance

¹⁵ There have been periods in which the amount for those in the islands was higher than that given to those in the mainland. According to our informants, such variations reflect shifting priorities of the Greek government.

has an in-kind character (reaching the amount of 1.140 euros) and may include the setting up of a small business (individually or in partnership), job placement (i.e. the payment of the returnee's on top of the salary at a new job), temporary accommodation (either the funding of the rent for some months, the funding of a renovation, or the funding of the house equipment to enhance living conditions), professional training programs, coverage of materials goods, medical assistance and treatment (i.e. hospitalisation, medicines, physiotherapies, or nursing staff).

The reintegration procedure is divided into three parts: development, implementation, and monitoring. The first part begins with a counselling session aiming at the agreement of a reintegration plan the implementation of which is then communicated with the IOM office in the country of return. Within one month after their return, migrants have to contact the IOM office in the country of return in order to launch the implementation of the plan or to negotiate its amendment if necessary, in collaboration with IOM Greece for the final approval (GRstakeholder5_2023).

'It's an amount that the person may need to complement with personal savings if they have any. But we have many, many examples where they did not have to put in any personal savings at all' (GRstakeholder5_2023).

The implementation that follows includes the necessary financial procedures. Monitoring takes place after three and six months of the payment, on the part of the IOM office in Greece, through the Monitoring Business (travel), by visiting or communicating with the returnee by phone, the Reintegration Program Monitoring, and the Reintegration Satisfaction Survey through MiMOSA (GRstakeholder5_2023). As evident, the *IOM Office in Greece maintains responsibility* for the implementation of reintegration in the country of return, highlighting the *transnational scale* of the procedure.

5.3 Materials and technologies used in AVRR in Greece

5.3.1 Materials

The multilevel and diverse geography of AVRR

Starting with geography and spatiality as a core element of materiality, AVRR can be seen to consist of a significant *network of places*, expanded all over Greece, and constantly 'moving' and *transforming* to cover existing needs. More particularly, IOM's presence in Greece includes the headquarters in Athens (located in Alimos at the Southern suburbs of the city), an office in Thessaloniki, and the permanent presence in Ioannina, Korinth, Patra, Drama, Evros, the island of Crete, and the five Aegean islands (Chios, Kos, Leros, Lesvos, Samos) where CCACs or Hotspots are operating (IOM, 2023), showing a significant *dispersal* as shown in Map 1. In Athens, OCAVRR, the IOM's Airport office, and the Airport also maintain an important role.

At the same time, a large number of other places also emerge, in remote and constantly changing areas of migrants' presence where IOM outreach assistants units (*'klimakia'*) are dispersed through regular visits when IOM's local office is not capable of approaching (GRstakeholder2_2023). Such places include a variety of different facilities (see 5.2.1), not only those where return procedures are put into practice (e.g. PRDCs), but also other *places of*

detention, and -importantly- *places of asylum, reception*, and accommodation, such as the hotspots and the mainland reception camps (GRstakeholder2_2023). Thus, *the implementation of returns is intertwined with the implementation (and the infrastructures) of detention and asylum/reception in the same spaces of the country*, as also Spathopoulou et al. (2022) argued for the case of Hotspots. In other words, the official asylum/reception spaces function also to facilitate the implementation of returns leading to a question on the complementary function of return and asylum (infrastructures) or a continuum between the two. The shrinkage of spatial and temporal distance between reception, rejection, and return processes appears to be a systemic objective, something that is also illustrated by the ‘early’ detention in the RICs, solely for identification reasons, as mentioned in 4.2.

Map 2. AVRR in Greece: IOM’s offices and places of permanent presence.
Source: IOM, 2023.

These places are *subject to change*, while lately, a trend of *organizational multiplication* is becoming evident, through the addition of either new places where IOM is present, or other places related to the return procedure in general. A characteristic example is that, after a request from IOM, the GAS office located close to the IOM’s headquarters, started to accept and provide services to applicants who needed to resign their asylum claims or statuses to avoid moving to the distant GAS headquarters, thus making the procedure faster and simpler (GRstakeholder1_2024). This new function of the GAS office for AVRR returnees was further enhanced, as in May 2023 two return counsellors were added to the personnel for the first time (GRstakeholder16_2024)¹⁶. Apart from IOM’s effectiveness in achieving small operational

¹⁶ Another example of the ‘dispersal’ and ‘expansion’ of return places (apart from AVRR) is the function of the Airport Police Station and of a newly established GAS unit at the airport. It has been observed,

transformations in the Greek administrative system, the above highlights the *dynamic character of AVRR geography*, constantly shifting especially through the multiplication and dispersal of the infrastructure's spaces.

OCAVRR

OCAVRR, the open facility for temporary accommodation of returnees in Athens, was established in 2015 in collaboration with the RIS, as a separate program from AVRR. IOM considers OCAVRR as an 'alternative measure to detention' (IOM, 2023: 32). It is located in Galatsi, a municipality bordering Athens, close to the center of the city, and to hospitals, embassies, consulates, and transportation. It offers accommodation to the most vulnerable AVRR participants, such as single parents, pregnant women, migrants with medical needs, the elderly, and the homeless¹⁷, either for the whole return process or for part of it, (as in the case of people residing outside Athens but visiting Athens for the issuance of their documents). Certain rules and regulations apply in OCAVRR, as in other accommodation facilities, including their residents' obligation to be present during the regular population verification (Papatzani et al., 2022). IOM representatives consider OCAVRR as a key asset of AVRR and an exemplary facility altogether. As one of them commented, *'the facility in Galatsi is a model one. I wish all European countries had similar facilities. It is unique in Europe'* (GRstakeholder1_2024).

Picture 1. OCAVRR. Source: Google street view.

Picture 2. OCAVRR. Source: IOM, 2020.

OCAVRR is located in a renovated building that is spatially and aesthetically in harmony with its residential surroundings. It has a capacity of approximately 100 people, and at the time of

that during the last few years, the police frequently transfer foreign detainees to the Airport Police Station as so-called 'alternates', in case some of the listed returnees of the specific operation are exempted from the procedure for various reasons. These 'alternates' have to spend the night at the airport before returning to the place of detention again (Greek Ombudsman, 2023). Moreover, since July 2022, a special unit of the GAS is present at the Airport during removal procedures to quickly address any pending issues on the administrative files of returnees, particularly to assess the admissibility of any subsequent asylum claims of returnees (Greek Ombudsman, 2023).

¹⁷ Unaccompanied minors and victims of trafficking are accommodated in other facilities under the responsibility of state authorities.

our research visit, it accommodated about 40 people. From September 2019 to August 2023, 2,482 migrants had been accommodated (IOM, 2023). The rooms in OCAVRR may host from three up to eight or 10 people, especially in the case of families, respecting the criterion of preserving and protecting family unity. Gender also plays a role in the distribution of residents, while language or ethnicity is also considered to some extent. Medical issues as well as psychosocial criteria are also important (GRstakeholder9_2023). The facility follows particular rules for accessibility, including the existence of a room on the ground floor for people using a wheelchair, while rooms on the first floor accommodate those in need of closer attention, as they are closer to the services on the ground floor.

OCAVRR is an open facility, meaning that those residing in it may enter and exit as they wish, yet after passing the control checks during their entrance and exit, and by using their AVRR card. It should be mentioned that OCAVRR is currently the most well-organised, and comprehensive urban accommodation facility in Athens and Greece, while addressed to people subject to return. In sharp contrast, urban accommodation facilities addressed to asylum seekers subject to protection and beneficiaries of protection subject to integration and housing services provisions have been absent since the termination of the ESTIA program in late 2022 (Kandyliis, Papatzani and Polyzou 2024; Papatzani, 2024) and the current termination of IOM HELIOS program (IOM, 2024d).

Figure 2. Sketch of an OCAVRR room of six places/beds on the first floor.
Source: E. Papatzani, GAPs field notes in Greece, 2023.

A multiplicity of materials that matter

A multiplicity of materials forms the basis of AVRR implementation, and –apart from the buildings, facilities, places described above– include various mundane objects, such as informative campaign material in many languages (see section 4.1), the IOM registration card of AVRR participants, the IOM returnees’ bag, the financial assistance, the in-kind provisions

for reintegration, an IOM van, vouchers for lunch during transit flights, a welcome kit, hygiene items during COVID-19, a large number of IOM papers, forms, and lists necessary for the implementation of AVRR (e.g. Voluntary Return Declaration & Consent form, Registration form, Check-list & Quality Control lists, the ‘fit-to-travel’ confirmation documents, Risk Assessment form, Rapid Vulnerability Screening form, Social Background form, Best Interest Determination form, the business plan form, to name just a few) (GRstakeholder1_2023; GRstakeholder3_2023; GRstakeholder4_2023).

One material object that shapes AVRR on a mundane level is the IOM white plastic bag (Picture 3, also see Annex I), which is given to AVRR participants before their departure and which they are instructed to carry with them when at the airport so that they can collect all the necessary documents and be identifiable by the staff in the crowded airport environment. At the same time, IOM bags are quite easily mistaken for the duty-free bags that are a familiar sight in airports: what is so detectable for the trained eye can be almost invisible to common passengers. The bag also helps recognise AVRR returnees when arriving at the country of return, during their entry checks by the authorities.

Picture 3. The IOM returnees’ bag. Source: K. Vezyrgianni, GAPs fieldwork in Greece, 2023.

The bag, thus, has multiple functions; it may be seen as an element of crowd control at the airport, a sign of the migrants’ status as returnees, a tool to distinguish them, or a way to discreetly cover their identity (Kandylis, Papatzani and Hatziprokopiou, 2024), in a relational space of differential and uneven mobilities and countless trajectories that intersect (Rozakou, 2022). It can also be seen as a sign for co-returnees sharing this same space and trajectory. Taking a bag as a starting point can reveal that such diverse and mundane materials matter (Kandylis et al., 2024), even if often remain invisible, and they constantly change in relation to multiple trajectories and geographies to shape migration infrastructures.

Picture 4. The IOM bag carried by Georgian returnees during a return operation at the airport. Source: K. Vezyrgianni, GAPs fieldwork in Greece, 2023.

Picture 5. The IOM bag carried by Georgian returnees during a return operation at the airport. Source: K. Vezyrgianni, GAPs fieldwork in Greece, 2023.

5.3.2 Technologies

A range of technologies are also used in different steps of AVRR. These include information dissemination technologies (i.e. the use of social media for informative campaigns and advertisements), return and reintegration counselling through communication platforms such as WhatsApp or Viber, the MiMOSA (Migrant Management Operational System Application) system, the OCAVRR database, the AVRR registration card, the OSA Platform for arranging a registration appointment, AVRR/OCAVRR Helplines, the Amadeus system for flight bookings, and control equipment and security cameras, among others.

MiMOSA, used by IOM globally (IOM, 2015), is the central IOM Greece digital platform for registering the demographic and biographical data of migrants and the whole process and steps of the return, accessible by IOM in different countries. Each entry for an AVRR applicant is given a personal identification number/code for purposes of personal data protection, functioning as a single and unique identifier of the person until the return to their country and the implementation of the reintegration.

‘For us, the beneficiaries are clearly persons, they are humans, but among each other, we communicate using their code, to avoid the leaking of personal data’ (GRstakeholder1_2024).

Apart from innovative tools, technological solutions that are selected for the management of the return process are also reflected in mundane objects. For example, the registration card owned by AVRR participants emerged as of particular importance, as it indicates that the particular person is in the middle of a return process. It notes their name, personal details, identification code, and photo, and it is used during the entrance and exit from OCAVRR as well as for the verification of the migrants’ potential long absence from the facility. Recently, a reference to the residency of the migrant and a phone number of OCAVRR was added, to highlight that the migrant’s residence is stable and known, and to provide the possibility to police authorities to contact IOM for identification during regular street controls (GRstakeholder9_2023).

5.4 Relations (interactions and frictions) between actors, materials and technologies in AVRR in Greece

5.4.1 Collaborations/networks of facilitating and contesting actors

The implementation of AVRR involves a significant range of networks and collaborations between the multiple actors already mentioned in 5.1, mainly revolving around IOM, according to particular needs and challenges that emerge.

Box 2. Collaborations between actors involved in AVRR in Greece

Collaborations are multiple and emerge in every step of the AVRR procedure described in 5.2. As the key actor of the infrastructure, IOM develops a large variety of relationships of collaboration, among others, with:

- The MMA, in cases of amendment needs and reallocation of the budget, as happened after the increase of medical cases, or when needed for the information outreach visits in different facilities
- The GAS for those that have to resign their asylum status but also for information exchange with IOM Outreach about new potential participants.
- With the RIS for the operation of the OCAVRR.
- The police authorities and the MCP for issuing return decisions, as well as the police Department at the Athens International Airport to assist in the cash assistance delivery to the migrants at the gate.
- Consulate authorities, migrant communities, the Greek authorities, health care providers, EASO, or municipal and regional authorities for organizing informative seminars and dissemination events.
- Consulate authorities in Greece and in other countries (for countries with no diplomatic office in Greece) for the verification and issuance of necessary travel documents.
- IOM and the Ministries of Foreign Affairs of return countries to receive the returnee at the airport to get landing permission.
- The IOM offices in transit or origin countries for the operation and reintegration procedures.
- Greek social services such as the National Centre for Social Solidarity, the Special Secretary, and Shelters for Unaccompanied Minors for protection issues that may emerge.
- With the AEMY operating in PRDCs providing health care and psychosocial support to detainees.
- With several NGOs for legal issues and NGOs providing medical services (BABEL Day Centre, Medecins du Monde, Médecins Sans Frontières, PRAXIS), the social pharmacy of the medical association, as well as public hospitals, the public hospitals' social services, and a private clinic.
- Several private companies for the operation of OCAVRR.
- With particular airlines agreed at a central level with IOM Geneva for low-fare tickets, re-bookings, and cancellations without penalty fees.
- With members of the returnees' families who are contacted before the return operation for protection issues.

The Greek authorities and especially the MMA are the closest collaborators of IOM, engaged in an ‘almost everyday communication, [...] not impersonal at all’ (GRstakeholder1_2024). This is reflected in the management of OCAVRR in which both IOM and the RIS are involved. The latter is responsible for general supervision¹⁸ while the IOM is the focal point for the overall coordination of provided services and the units involved.

Collaborations are subject to a strict division of labor and roles, based on the particular mandate and jurisdiction of the actors involved, as well as to power relations. At the same time, however, ad hoc practices are sometimes employed to bypass strict role divisions or bureaucracy. A characteristic example is the fact that for IOM Outreach personnel to enter the reception camps, approval should be provided by MMA (GRstakeholder2_2023), while for entering police departments there are cases of ‘routine unstated agreement’ (GRstakeholder2_2023) without the requirement of authorities’ approval.

The embassies and consulates in Greece and abroad also constitute close collaborators of IOM and inform IOM about possible changes in the procedures (i.e. regarding the geographic scope of the laissez-passer) and the circumstances in return countries (i.e. restrictions related to full or partial suspension) (GRstakeholder3_2023).

Collaborations are not stable throughout time, but flexible, dynamic, and subject to change. This is evident, for example, in the doings of the medical team of OCAVRR. More particularly, collaborations with public hospitals gave at different points in time their place to the collaboration with a private clinic which ‘*we use in case we cannot arrange an appointment immediately*’ (GRstakeholder1_2024). The IOM’s Operation Department may also collaborate with the public hospitals’ social services to arrange and coordinate patients’ movement to and from the hospital, especially in cases of special needs.

Beyond the national and the local level, the international scale is also present in collaborations and networks, as evident by the collaborations between IOM Greece, the IOM Geneva, and the IOM offices at the transit and origin countries. This is reflected in the reintegration procedure, for example, as IOM Greece is responsible for reintegration in the country of origin after return.

Additionally, several actors may maintain a double role at times, either as collaborating or as opposing and contesting ones. Immigrant communities, for example, are often critical of AVRR, but may also inform their members about the program, maintain close contacts with IOM, or escort their members to IOM offices when the latter are not familiar with movements in the city (GRstakeholder12_2024). IOM representatives also mentioned that instead of being criticised by the migrant communities they usually receive ‘claims for more collaboration, for individuals who want to get into the program, who need help’ (GRstakeholder1_2024).

The police also constitute an actor maintaining a double role. As a collaborating actor, IOM arranges appointments with the police, for the latter to issue the return decision. Moreover, after IOM’s requests, police departments inform IOM about arrests of people potentially eligible for AVRR (GRstakeholder2_2023); they are also responsible for AVRR participants in detention centers, as well as for their transfer to the airport.

¹⁸ This includes decisions on cases of termination of material reception conditions, i.e. when a migrant should be expelled from OCAVRR according to the legal framework, or on cases when someone that had previously left OCAVRR wants to be accommodated again (GRstakeholder9_2023).

5.4.2 Tensions/oppositions of actors

Conflicting relationships and oppositions with AVRR may also arise from these actors. The above-mentioned acts of *migrant communities do not necessarily reflect a positive stance and perception* of AVRR. The Pakistani Community, for example, does not consider respective returns as ‘voluntary’ and refers to many shortcomings. For example, they mention that an increase in the amount of the in-kind reintegration assistance would not be the authorities’ goal because it would enhance migration movements both from and back to the country of origin (GRstakeholder12_2024).

On behalf of IOM, no specific tensions with the Greek authorities were mentioned reminding Pécoud’s (2018) argument that IOM generally abstains from criticism of its member-states’ authorities. Regarding especially the police, its relations with AVRR appear also to be - indirectly - competitive. This is related to the fact that as the actor responsible for forced returns, the police wish to show efficiency to the extent of its jurisdiction: as one of our IOM informants commented during our visit to the airport, ‘they are also interested in increasing their numbers’. Another field of potential tension has to do with the fact that in cases of arrests of AVRR participants, after confirming their registration in AVRR, they are not set free but led to detention where they are kept until the return operation (GRstakeholder10_2024). This treatment on the part of the police was characterised by an IOM interviewee as an instance of ‘different management’ of the undocumented situation of the returnee (GRstakeholder9_2023). Yet, as mentioned later, the fact that AVRR does not protect participants from detention constitutes a serious shortcoming of the program.

Tensions have also emerged regarding the AVRR and OCAVRR participants’ free and public access to health care provision in public hospitals, a broader issue concerning a large number of migrants in Greece. More particularly, tensions had to do with the practices of particular doctors or the hospitals’ administrations that contested migrants’ rights to free health care. To overcome such obstacles, the OCAVRR medical team made reference to the existing legal framework on medical prescription documents provided to migrants when they visited the hospital. Furthermore, based on a report by an OCAVRR doctor, the RIS, as the OCAVRR management authority, sent letters to hospital administrations to facilitate access to free healthcare provision for OCAVRR participants.

Tensions with the local communities emerged during the establishment of OCAVRR. The first building was publicly-owned and selected in 2013-‘14 in cooperation with Greek authorities. It is located in Ag. Varvara, a municipality at the west of Athens, and its selection was met with opposition from local residents; groups with different political perspectives, both some of them xenophobic and the rest contesting the voluntary character of AVRR. That particular choice was abandoned and the current building owned by a private landlord in Galatsi was selected (GRstakeholder9_2023). During the initial period of settling into the new neighbourhood, there were occasional tensions, with some people accusing OCAVRR residents of any incidents of delinquency, thus linking migrants with criminality: ‘*Okay, there are people who will be negative [...] and at the first opportunity they will complain [...] the first direction they will turn will be against the facility*’ (GRstakeholder9_2023).

Overall, the relationships between actors are complex and dynamic, as well as subject to change. Alongside a strict division of labour and roles, as well as particular power relations, ad hoc practices sometimes circumvent these divisions or bureaucratic relations. Networks and collaborations are numerous and, importantly, multiscale, while tensions and oppositions may emerge between collaborating actors, some of whom maintain a double role. The dynamic

nature, flexibility and ability to transform characterise the relations that constitute the RMI of AVRR in Greece.

5.4.3 Flows of funding, activities, databases, materials between these actors and networks

Since 2016, AVRR programs are co-funded 75% by the EU Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) and 25% national funds. Past projects were financed by other sources, including the former European Return Fund, EEA Grants, the UK government, the Swiss State Secretariat for Migration, the Norwegian Directorate for Immigration, and AMIF Emergency Funds (IOM, 2019a: Annex I). The overall EU financial support from the EU for AVRR during the programming period 2021-27 is 35.5 million¹⁹.

AVRR includes multiple flows of funding, resources, materials, and technologies between actors, as already evident in the aforementioned. A characteristic example is the negotiations between IOM and the MMA regarding the funding, as happened after the increase of medical cases and the respective need of amendment and reallocation of the budget that emerged.

Moreover, of particular importance is the flow of funding, materials, and databases between the IOM office in Greece and in the return country for reintegration steps, where IOM Greece maintains most of the responsibility for reintegration of the migrant in the country of origin after return. It is the IOM office in Greece that provides the financial assistance, after exchanges between the IOM offices related to the finalisation of the reintegration plan, the collection of documents and their check by IOM Greece, the monitoring of the plan in cooperation with the IOM office in return country, or the constant use of MiMOSA. According to IOM interviewees, this has to do with the source of funding: 'funding comes from Greece. Basically, whoever has the funding is responsible' (GRstakeholder5_2023).

The management of reintegration funding in countries of return has been a thorny issue, occasionally raising suspicions and discontent among our migrant informants²⁰ (Papatzani et al., 2025). Although unconfirmed by our research, allegations concerning informal 'deals' or bribes (with local IOM officials in countries of return or with airport/border officials) or 'synergies' among the local IOM and specific shopkeepers have been voiced (GRmigrant16_2024; GRmigrant26_2024), raising questions about alternative ways of handling the reintegration funding.

5.4.4 Challenges and implementation gaps between different actors' agendas and actions

Our research revealed that a number of challenges and implementation gaps emerge in the everyday workings of AVRR infrastructure in Greece, creating crucial shortcomings in the procedure. These include several communication and collaboration gaps, the risk of arrest and detention of AVRR participants, delays and unequal temporalities, emerging processes of irregularisation, tensions and ambiguity between voluntariness and coercion, and trends of re-

¹⁹ See European Commission, Migration Management in Greece, Financial Support from the EU: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migration-management/migration-management-greece/financial-support-eu_en. Accessed 26/05/2025.

²⁰ Interviews with migrants were conducted in the context of WP7 of GAPs (see Papatzani et al., 2025).

migration after return that highlight the non-linearity of migration trajectories. These issues are discussed below. As is evident from the above, such challenges affect the nature of AVRR directly, calling into question its ‘voluntariness’, and directly impacting migrants’ experiences.

Communication and collaboration gaps

Communication and collaboration issues have emerged between the IOM and certain authorities, particularly in camps where IOM units are operating. For example, it is common for the MMA camp authorities to fail to inform IOM Outreach on the new arrivals, as in the case of Malakasa camp in Attica (GRstakeholder2_2023). This means that IOM staff find it hard to inform those who arrived recently about AVRR ‘and, given that the information is provided on an individual basis, [they] are obliged to go door-to-door in the containers to inform the new arrivals’ (GRstakeholder2_2023).

Another point raised particularly on the part of migrant communities has to do with delays in AVRR created due to organisational choices of IOM. As they see it, IOM usually puts people in a situation of waiting for months, in order to gather a significant number of returnees before proceeding with the flight, and this is a reason why many interested people do not choose to return through AVRR (GRstakeholder14_2024; GRstakeholder12_2024). Another issue concerns the lower amount of financial aid that the AVRR participants residing on the islands receive, compared to those residing on the Greek mainland, resulting in the unequal treatment of migrants depending on the place of registration. When asked about the reasons behind this differential treatment, one of our interviewees (GRstakeholder1_2024) responded that it is explained by the priority given by the government to return operations from the mainland, while in the past the allocation of the amount was different.

The risk of arrest and detention of AVRR participants

In what concerns the role of the police mentioned above, AVRR and OCAVVR participants are also at *risk of arrest and detention* despite their registration for voluntary return. As mentioned by IOM interviewees, certain changes have been made to the AVRR card (mentioned in 5.3) in an attempt to reduce the possibility of arrest by the police. However, even in such cases, the police are likely to arrest and detain AVRR participants (GRstakeholder1_2023), which is described by one IOM interviewee as a ‘gap’ in the procedure (GRstakeholder9_2023). Although IOM continues the AVRR process in detention in such cases, such a procedure is a serious flaw in the program, as it applies seemingly uniform procedures to returnees who find themselves under obviously different circumstances.

Delays and unequal temporalities

The risk of arrest, and the fear thereof, has also to do with delays in the AVRR procedure. Delays are usually related to the issuance of papers by the consulates. As mentioned by an IOM interviewee, ‘*if their embassy is late in issuing a temporary travel document, for example, it is very likely that they will not be able to return and will walk the streets in fear*’ (GRstakeholder9_2023). Moreover, delays are also related to the returnee’s legal status: those without a return decision must engage in bureaucratic procedures with the authorities (as mentioned below) before they can proceed. Delays may also be caused by the necessary medical and health checks to confirm fitness to travel. The above issues emerging in the AVRR

procedure can create different –and unequal– temporalities for people registered in the program and their particular versions of the experience.

Processes of irregularisation

As mentioned in 5.2.2, the enrolment in AVRR presupposes that the applicants withdraw their asylum applications, and refrain from any rights coming with a real or potential regular status – either of an international protection beneficiary or a migrant with a valid stay permit or even the temporary ‘regularity’ of an asylum seeker. This process can be seen as a peculiar (self-)irregularisation, i.e. of accepting an irregular status, in order to take advantage of the benefits of AVRR. Moreover, one of our migrant informants²¹ commented that approaching IOM to enroll in the program was the first time he obtained any kind of ‘document’ in Greece. But certainly, this was only to be officially recognised as ‘irregular’ and prepare him to return.

We thus observe that irregularisation constitutes an important part of the implementation of AVRR in practice: Irregularity may be seen as an important pre-condition for the implementation and maintenance of AVRR, or in other words, AVRR seems to ‘regularise’ irregularisation, thus contributing to the reproduction of a return-irregularisation nexus.

Between voluntariness and coercion

For IOM, ‘freedom of choice’ and ‘informed decision’ for a return ‘based on one’s own will’ emerge as important issues (for an analysis, see Gauci, 2023) and the prerequisites for ‘voluntariness’. In IOM’s ‘Key migration terms’, in the context of AVRR ‘voluntariness is assumed to exist if two conditions apply: (a) freedom of choice, which is defined by the absence of physical or psychological pressure to enrol in an assisted voluntary return and reintegration program; and (b) an informed decision which requires the availability of timely, unbiased and reliable information upon which to base the decision’ (IOM, 2024a).

An informed decision is considered feasible by IOM after providing the migrant with adequate and accurate information about AVRR, as well as when there is no bias in deciding to return. Indeed, there have been cases in which AVRR participants, after receiving treatment for their medical condition, changed their mind and decided to stay in Greece instead of returning. As regards voluntariness, it should be mentioned that even if participation in AVRR is voluntary in the sense that any participant has the right to withdraw at any time, the wider context in which the program operates in Greece, defined by legal, political, and institutional arrangements, creates multiple limitations and obstacles for migrants’ choices and trajectories (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). Thus, the perceived voluntary nature of AVRR is questioned when this context and the circumstances in which a migrant takes his/her ‘informed decision’ are taken into account, and when the reasons for return for migrants are examined (Papatzani et al., 2025).

Multiple such reasons were revealed. One of the most common is the emergence of severe medical issues, which according to our IOM informants became more widespread among the returnees during the last few years, affecting either themselves or their family members in the countries of origin. Another reason is the non-possession of legal documents, despite the migrants’ long-term settlement in Greece, which reproduces precarity in everyday life. Psychological tiredness and depression due to the difficulties encountered during their stay in

²¹ Interview conducted in the context of WP7 of GAPs (Papatzani et al., 2025).

Greece or trauma created during the migration journey also matter (GRstakeholder4_2023) (Papatzani et al., 2025).

Questions on the voluntariness of AVRR also emerge when detention is considered. The relations between AVRR and detention are not mutually exclusive since AVRR procedures are implemented for migrants in detention centers who remain detained despite their declared willingness and consent to return. Moreover, migrants who register in AVRR while at liberty but get arrested by the police afterward may also end up in detention, despite that AVRR procedures have already started (Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024).

'Actually, they're not voluntary. Even those who, for example, some Pakistanis or even Iranians who want to return, [...] they are in the detention centers and they are tired, and they say I'm tired, I want to leave. [...] For me it is not voluntary, because they were forced to because of the situation' (GRstakeholder14_2024).

As mentioned above by the Pakistani Community representative, since the freedom of choice and the informed decision may be taken in the context and circumstances of detention, the character of voluntariness is seriously challenged. Thus, questions of coercion arise in the case of Greece as well as in other countries (Sahin-Mencutek et al., 2023; Sahin-Mencutek & Triandafyllidou, 2024) that challenge the perceived dichotomy between voluntary and forced returns.

Re-migration after return: the ephemeral nature of returns and the non-linearity of migration trajectories

Our research confirms that re-migration, namely migrating again to a country from where migrants returned, is an established migration trajectory also recognised by IOM (IOM, 2024b). The reasons vary, yet they often relate to livelihoods, increased cost of life, and health care services inaccessibility as well as to socio-political situations, gender, origin, religion etc. One of our IOM informants recognised this possibility and explained further IOM's official position:

'[...] according to IOM, sustainable reintegration is when a person has returned to his/her country of origin and with the assistance given, manages to reach levels of self-sufficiency, economic, social, and psychosocial dimension in all this part, to such a level that if he/she wants to emigrate again, it is a decision of his/her own and not out of necessity' (GRstakeholder5_2023).

Multiplicity and non-linearity are also the case of such circular trajectories. As the Athens Georgia House representative explained, Georgian nationals are permitted to stay for 90 days in Greece through a visa and later return to Georgia before moving again; in case they stay longer, they have to pay a fee (GRstakeholder15_2024). Return for them seems like a repeated 'choice' during their stay in Greece. Such trajectories may vary, based on different reasons and factors according to nationality, gender, experiences, and aspirations.

The multiplicity of trajectories does not only have to do with assisted returns but also with forced ones: as revealed by the Greek Ombudsman, the authority responsible for the external audit of forced returns in Greece, the main return reason for migrants from Albania is to have their detention lifted, and then to come back to Greece (GRstakeholder8_2023). At the same time, cases of multiple returns to Albania have also been reported (GRstakeholder8_2023).

Thus, re-migration challenges IOM's disciplinary rationality (Ahouga, 2024) and its goal of sustained re-integration and highlights the complexities and multiple parameters that need to be considered if AVRR is to successfully facilitate and support sustainable integration.

6. Concluding remarks

Alongside Greece's longstanding history of return policies and practices, the present Country Dossier illustrates that the implementation of returns involves a multiplicity of actors, numerous stages, and complex, non-linear procedures, supported by a continually expanding and adaptable range of materials and technologies.

The actors involved differ significantly in terms of institutional frameworks, scales of operation, procedural approaches, and funding mechanisms. Actors tasked with coordinating others often cultivate an entrepreneurial approach to decision-making to ensure procedural efficiency. Conversely, many actors' roles are characterised by ambiguities and a lack of coordination, which contributes to operational fragmentation. Central to the day-to-day functioning of the three RMIs in Greece is the role of the Hellenic Police. Furthermore, several actors actively challenge return operations, particularly in cases of pushbacks, by deploying innovative tools, methods, and resources to counteract these practices. Doings across all RMI types are inherently non-linear, exhibiting diverse spatial and temporal dimensions and frequently displaying operational inconsistencies. For example, detention may occur at border points before the issuance of a return or expulsion decision, or return orders may be issued to new arrivals who express an intention to apply for asylum. *Detention, the threat of detention, and processes of irregularisation remain fundamental components of all RMIs.*

The above observations reveal the systematic and operational nature of all RMIs, including pushbacks, even though pushbacks constitute an out-of-law mode of return. Recent developments indicate that all types of returns in Greece have not only been institutionalised but, more importantly, 'infrastructuralised', in the sense of acquiring particular operational features together with concrete (albeit shifting) materialities and geographies. This is evident in the organised networks connecting various actors, actions, materials, and technologies involved. In essence, the three Return Migration Infrastructures in Greece have evolved to exhibit both a stable, organised structure and a capacity for dynamic adaptation as circumstances demand.

As far as the AVRR is concerned, the analysis unpacks a complex network of actors operating across multiple scales, including the local, regional, national, and even the transnational, as the role that IOM Greece has in the implementation of the post-return reintegration plan reveals. Among these are non-state and private actors, who play a significant role in the daily functions of this infrastructure. Notably, some actors maintain a dual role, simultaneously cooperating with and contesting return operations. Certain actors maintain close collaborations, defined by a division of labour and clearly delineated roles that are however adjusted as necessary, often through ad hoc arrangements. Despite such close partnerships, communication and coordination gaps frequently arise, often due to existing power hierarchies. Although significant tensions regarding AVRR were not extensively reported, the local level remains critical; for example, some xenophobic and racist responses from local residents have been reported in the neighbourhood surrounding OCAVRR in Athens.

In the implementation of AVRR, significant variations and contingencies emerge in the processes experienced by migrants. The IOM's approach is marked by professionalism and an entrepreneurial and managerial mode of operation, aligning in part with market-inspired practices, as discussed by Pécoud (2018). This approach comprises, on one hand, a seemingly standardised and uniform procedure for all, while, on the other, a 'case-by-case' framework involving individualised assessments. These dual modes create contradictions, leading to different —and often unequal— experiences for AVRR applicants. First, the case-by-case

assessment is shaped by several factors, including applicants' legal status, possession of identification documents, vulnerabilities and medical conditions, entry points to the program (e.g. detention facilities), places of stay while awaiting return, and varying types of encounters with relevant authorities. These factors influence the procedural steps and actions applied to each applicant, resulting in different versions of the AVRR process. Consequently, applicants may experience various –and typically unequal– temporalities, spatial arrangements, and overall return experiences.

Second, the application of a standardised procedure for all AVRR participants fails to address pre-existing unequal positions, particularly for those in detention—whether they apply while detained or are detained as irregular after registering in AVRR. In these cases, the general structure of the process remains unchanged, encompassing all stages, from informational outreach to registration and protection, without adjustments for the detainees' circumstances. Thus, AVRR does not protect migrants from detention in an official way. Implementing 'protection' as part of the AVRR process within a detention context creates an inherently problematic and contradictory situation, directly challenging the voluntary nature of AVRR.

Further concerns arise when processes of irregularisation are considered, revealing a return-irregularisation nexus in which AVRR appears to be 'normalising' or 'regularising' irregularisation, in both legal and symbolic terms. While in some cases, particularly with highly vulnerable individuals, responsible actors may apply ad hoc practices or make exceptions to the uniform procedure to protect migrant well-being, the ceasing of detention is typically not among these exceptions. These observations suggest that the practices and the 'doings' forming Return Migration Infrastructures must be considered alongside the 'non-doings' of actors. From this perspective, it is clear that aspects of protection for AVRR applicants remain crucial, but are also absent from the program, echoing criticism of IOM's lack of commitment to human rights at the international level (Pécoud, 2018).

Funding, materials, and technologies play a crucial role in shaping the AVRR process. The flow of funding influences relationships between actors and facilitates specific doings on a transnational scale. Additionally, the importance of everyday mundane materials and the geographic and spatial contexts in which AVRR operates becomes evident, as these factors shape the infrastructure at multiple levels. The OCAVRR, as a well-organised, service-oriented urban facility designed for returnees, stands in contrast to the absence of urban facilities dedicated to the protection of asylum seekers and integration of protection beneficiaries. This disparity raises concerns about the state's priorities, particularly in terms of providing dignified living conditions solely for returnees, while neglecting similar provisions for asylum seekers and refugees.

The geography of AVRR, comprising a multi-layered and dispersed network of locations, offices, and units, is dynamic, constantly evolving and subject to change and expansion. Crucially, this network is not merely devoted to return but *exploits the existing geographies of the official asylum/reception and detention spaces which are used to facilitate the implementation of returns. Consequently, return and asylum infrastructures seem to be both intersecting and overlapping.*

The analysis further interrogates the voluntary character of AVRR by considering the context in which the 'informed decision' to participate is made and the factors influencing the 'freedom of choice'. As Gauci (2023) asserts, 'freedom of choice is defined by an absence of pressure rather than the presence of will', while 'only certain forms of pressure are acknowledged as undermining voluntariness', excluding others such as the economic and legal pressure (Gauci, 2023: 404). In this regard, while participation in AVRR is voluntary, in the

sense that participants have the right to withdraw at any time, the broader context in which the program operates in Greece is characterised by coercion (Kuschminder 2017: 4-5; Hatziprokopiou et al., 2024). The motivations for return illustrate the array of challenges and constraints that shape returnees' decisions, including the lack of legal documents, economic insecurity, limited opportunities for integration, prolonged detention, and worsening medical conditions (both in Greece and the EU) that severely impact migrants' ability to work and earn an income (Papatzani et al., 2025). Prolonged detention, with its associated psychological strain and trauma, may also be a key factor, if not one of the contexts, within which individuals decide to return.

Other scholars have argued that AVRR programs in general can be seen as projects of 'soft deportation' (Webber 2011; Cleton and Chauvin 2020), or 'disguised deportation' (Gauci, 2023), or 'self-deportation' (Spathopoulou et al., 2022), that risk being a 'facade' of 'voluntariness' for migrants who face 'the tough dilemma of absconding or departing "voluntarily"' (Triandafyllidou & Ricard-Guay, 2019). Rather than a true alternative to deportation, as promoted by governments and other actors implementing assisted returns, scholars have argued that AVRR suggests 'a transformation within the regime of deportation itself' (Fine and Walters, 2021: 3061). What emerges from the above analysis is that voluntary and forced returns should be understood more as a continuum of various levels of coercion rather than an absolute dichotomy (Sahin-Mencutek et al., 2023; Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou, 2024). These dynamics are closely linked to the multiplicity, non-linearity, and circularity of migration trajectories, as well as the transient nature of returns, which were highlighted in our research. Even for AVRR participants, returning to Greece after having been sent back to their country of origin is not an uncommon occurrence (Papatzani et al., 2025).

As a policy recommendation, authorities and relevant actors should consider disentangling AVRR from detention by: i) ensuring the cessation of detention of individuals as soon as they register for AVRR, and ii) refraining from arresting individuals who possess documentation confirming their participation in the program. Furthermore, participation in AVRR programs should preferably be an option for those living autonomously rather than those accommodated in massive facilities, such as reception and accommodation camps, particularly when they are in vulnerable psychosocial state following arduous migration journeys, as this practice disregards and undermines individuals' intention to seek asylum or their need for protection. There remains an urgent need for the (re-)establishment of dignified urban spaces for accommodation, reception, and the development of integration opportunities. This is especially crucial given the recent trend of policies that appear to be moving in the opposite direction, limiting opportunities, enhancing returns, and fostering irregularisation.

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Annexes

1. Ethnographic notes from the observation of a departure of Georgian AVRR returnees at the El. Venizelos Athens International Airport.

The following text is a synthesis of the ethnographic notes of three researchers of the EKKE team who were present at the return process.

On Thursday, November 2, 2023, a three-member team from EKKE had the opportunity to conduct ethnographic observation during the final procedures for the return of 37 migrants to Georgia, on an Aegean Airlines flight departing from the Athens International Airport. The research visit was organised together with the IOM personnel who gave us the permission to participate, prepared the necessary documents and explained to us every step of the procedure as it was unfolding.

Our team arrives at the airport half an hour before the scheduled 9:00 p.m. meeting time. The flight departs at 11:45 p.m., a choice that ensures relatively low passenger traffic at the airport, thus facilitating group monitoring and control. A group of approximately 20 Georgian migrants is already at the meeting point in Terminal A1 for non-Schengen departures. They are gathered just inside the main entrance, in a waiting area with some seats. We immediately recognize them by the large white bags with the IOM logo, which we have often heard about during interviews.

The group includes mostly women, along with several men and children of various ages, including an infant and three school-aged children, some elderly women —one accompanied by her daughter— an elderly man, several families, single mothers with children, and many young individuals (mostly women) who do not speak Greek. Surrounding them are small and large pieces of luggage. We assume that some may be accompanying friends and relatives who are departing tonight, although we cannot tell exactly how many. We also assume that some may know each other already or may have just met now. The atmosphere is relatively calm and quiet, with low-toned conversations and some movement, mostly due to children and because there aren't enough seats for everyone.

We initially sit a little apart and, for a short time, outside. Then, we approach the group of migrants, standing and waiting for the IOM team to arrive. A woman standing behind us was making a video call, happily showing the airport on her phone. One of us starts a conversation with some of the people, including a Georgian woman over 50. When asked in Greek if they were waiting for the IOM, she replied, 'they told us to come here at 9 and wait with the bag'. This woman has been in Greece for the past year. Before that, she lived in Georgia and had previously spent six years in Greece. She was happy to be leaving because her family is there. When we asked if she was considering returning to Greece, she replied, 'We'll see!' She was traveling with her cousin, who was of the same age, sitting next to her and also speaking Greek.

A few minutes after 9:00 p.m., the four-member IOM team arrives, including two Outreach staff members from IOM headquarters to assist with crowd control, and two members of the Airport Team. They wear badges with IOM insignia around their necks, and as we were informed, they will soon also wear special vests displaying the new donor. As they told us, an interpreter is not needed in this case, but one is available if required. One member of the IOM team explains the steps of the process to us while the other team members begin gathering the migrants around them: 'Come over here, all those traveling'. A woman has lost the cross she

was wearing around her neck and is searching for it among the standing bodies and seats. Our presence is noticeable but, as expected in an airport, does not attract particular attention.

The first document check begins. The IOM staff members provide instructions in Greek, occasionally switching to English for some individuals. They review a folder containing a consolidated list with participants' details (full name, AMIF personal identification number/code, age, gender, country of origin), ticket information for each person, copies of their travel documents, a form listing their names for signing upon receipt of financial assistance after passport verification, and some additional documents as needed in individual cases. Besides the IOM bag, the returnees carry the return decision interoffice memo issued by the police (all except those over 80 and children who are registered on their mother's document or on their father's if unaccompanied by their mother), other specific documents as needed, their travel documents (most had passports, but there were also some with laissez-passer), and their AVRR card (all have one except children, who are listed as accompanying members on their mother's card or on their father's if the mother is absent). The returnees are recorded on the list, and the return decision interoffice memo and AVRR cards are collected by IOM staff, who then hand out ticket copies to the migrants. In conversations among themselves, staff members refer to the participants by their identification codes. For example, they refer to a mother with a child as '636 is with 637'. The entire process was carried out by IOM in a methodical and highly organised manner. There was no need to explain anything beforehand; the migrants did not seem to have any questions, and there were no significant delays.

When the check is completed, the IOM team arranges the returnees in a line to count them: 'We'll do a cross-check to see if everyone is here. Let's see if it's 37!' Instructions are given for those not traveling to stand separately, and they step a few paces away. Here, the process takes on a sense of 'crowd control' for the first time. Once the count is completed, it is found that ten people are missing. They decide to move on to the next phase, leaving one IOM team member behind to manage the remaining ten individuals.

The staff gives instructions to proceed to check-in, and the lines start moving. An elderly woman from Georgia is concerned about her medication and struggles to carry her luggage. We help her, and she thanks us, apologising as well. We ask her in Greek if she is happy to be returning, and with a broad smile, she replies, 'very much'. She hasn't been to Georgia in 20 years and will meet her two daughters-in-law and grandchildren for the first time. They will be waiting for her at the airport, and then they have a journey ahead to her village.

The check-in takes place at counters 110, 111, 112, and 113 and is mixed with other passengers on the flight, the majority of whom are from AVRR. The migrants who had arrived late are now here as well. Members of the IOM team inform the airline staff at the counter: 'Everyone here is going to Tbilisi!' and they stand at the front, personally handing over passports to the airline staff and helping with luggage. In the check-in line, some people seem to know each other from before. A woman in front of us says she met the others during the IOM briefing, but there seems to be a greater familiarity between some of them. We talk in Greek with an elderly woman who is returning to Georgia after 20 years. She has a bag of chocolates, likely gifts for relatives and friends there, and she worries that they might be taken during the personal items check. She will be traveling alone, accompanied by her daughter (around 40 years old) and a man who came to see her off at the airport. In the check-in line, some people say their goodbyes to relatives and friends, and a few become emotional.

When check-in is completed, instructions are given to move forward and line up to be counted. Now, there is a single line facing the direction of the passport control. We continue moving, alongside the group, each time they move. No one seems bothered or puzzled by our

presence. We pass through the boarding pass control, with a member of the IOM team doing the counting, while the staff member at the counter watches indifferently.

IOM takes us to the airport police office to hand over our IDs and receive tags from the Hellenic Police (ELAS), as our names had been approved in advance. On the front, they are labeled 'ELAS Special Permit', and on the back, there are several details that are not easily distinguishable, such as the fact that they are the property of the Police. They are well-worn. Later, we will learn that they are used by police officers who are involved in the transfer of detainees.

This is followed by the police check of travel documents and return decision interoffice memo for the returnees. The identification code is written with a pen on each individual's boarding pass, which is then photographed for IOM's records. The documents, such as the interoffice memo, are stamped by the police, while the travel documents are scanned. Afterward, the travel documents and boarding passes are returned to the migrants. Throughout this process, IOM team members work closely with the police inside and outside the control booth, and there seems to be a strong rapport between them, joking as though they are colleagues from the same service.

The file with the original stamped interoffice memo and copies of passports collected by the IOM employee is handed over to the police and locked in a police vault, with the key held by IOM. In the morning, the airport police duty officer retrieves the file and sends it to the Foreigners Department to register that these individuals have returned to their home country. If the flight involves detainees, they are accompanied by three service notes. One is kept by the police officer escorting them, the second by the airport police (IOM's file that goes into the vault), and the third is taken by IOM because no photocopy of the service note was made beforehand.

Next, the returnees proceed behind the booth where two additional IOM staff members, in addition to the four already present, are handling the distribution of money to each individual passing through the check. One reads the identification code on the boarding pass. The other holds the folder, opens it in front of them, shows the two 500-euro notes, and hands it over. He repeats phrases such as '1,000 euros, please' or '2,000 euros, please, thank you' (for families). The migrants sign a receipt list. Some say 'thank you', while others remain silent. A few blush. The IOM employee maintains a detached demeanour. Some young Georgian women further down in the line made a breeze with the folder containing the money, laughing. This moment of handing over the money was, at least for us, quite awkward. We avoid looking at the transaction for more than a moment at a time. We have the sense that some feel embarrassed.

They move a little further, where another IOM staff member takes a photo of the boarding pass with the identification code written on it. They wait until everyone has finished and move on. As we continue, in the personal items check line, we chat with a young couple in English. The woman said she had been in Greece for a little over a year. With no desire to speak more, she casually remarked something like, 'your country is nice, but goodbye now'. We all passed through the personal items check.

For the departure gates, we didn't take the usual route through the duty-free shops like the other passengers. Instead, we passed through a 'hidden' door that had been locked until then, leading directly to the waiting area for the gates. A member of the IOM team explained that we used this door to avoid the group getting lost in the shops and causing delays and also to prevent the money given to the returnees from being spent in the stores. As we learned, there is a clear instruction for returnees not to spend the financial assistance at the airport, because if the flight is canceled, they would be required to return the entire amount. Aside from

drinking water, they are not allowed to sit for coffee or shop at the duty-free stores while waiting.

Picture 6. Part of the airport and the door on the left of the duty free shops leading directly to the gates. Source: T. Psallidaki, GAPs fieldwork in Greece, 2023.

We head towards gate A9. At A8, the group stops standing next to some seats in a line for a count. An IOM staff member, with a hint of mild intensity, loudly says, ‘I want to see your IOM bags’. Once the headcount is complete, everyone sits down in the waiting area. We also sit, keeping some distance from the migrants, and chat with one of the IOM team members. He describes the difficulties in managing groups on flights with many returnees, mentioning, for example, that ‘this toilet has an exit on the other side’. He is also aware that ‘three people requested to go to the toilet’. The group headcount is often repeated for tighter control. During the 2.5 hours we were there, the group was counted 8 times, both directly and indirectly.

When boarding begins, the migrants stand up without any announcement. They now mix with the other passengers on the flight (except for first-class passengers, who board first). The boarding process is completed in a few minutes, and the departure will occur with minimal delay. There are no strong displays of emotion, nor any notable farewells directed toward the IOM staff or us.

We retrace our steps with the IOM staff. We all go together to the airport police office to return our identification tags. There are more police officers there now, both in uniform and one in civilian clothes, and they exchange friendly banter with the IOM staff, joking and discussing the schedule for the next day.

When asked about the situation with detainees, an IOM staff member tells us that there are no issues, because ‘when they arrive here, even if they didn't want to return in the past, they’ve made up their minds now’. They add that detainees have good relations with the police, ‘they’ve known each other for years’, ‘we know the guys’, ‘I don't know what it was like in the past, but now...’.

We say our goodbyes to the IOM staff near the terminal entrance and thank them.

2. List of WP3 Interviews

N.	Interview ID	Type of stakeholder	Organization / Institution
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1	GRstakeholder1_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece, Athens
2	GRstakeholder2_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
3	GRstakeholder3_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
4	GRstakeholder4_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
5	GRstakeholder5_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
6	GRstakeholder6_2023	NGO	Refugee Support Aegean (RSA)
7	GRstakeholder7_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece, office in Thessaloniki
8	GRstakeholder8_2023	Official Institutions related to returns' monitoring	The Greek Ombudsman
9	GRstakeholder9_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
10	GRstakeholder10_2023	International Organisation	IOM Greece
11	GRstakeholder11_2024	Independent authority	Greek National Commission for Human Rights (GNCHR)
12	GRstakeholder12_2024	Migrants and Refugees Organisations	Pakistani Community in Greece
13	GRstakeholder13_2024	NGO, Legal advocacy	Greek Council for Refugees (GCR)
14	GRstakeholder14_2024	NGO, Information, Awareness, Advocacy	Greek Forum of Refugees
15	GRstakeholder15_2024	Migrants and Refugees Organisations	Athens Georgian House
16	GRstakeholder16_2024	Authorities/ Policy makers / Officials	Ministry of Migration and Asylum, Directorate of Returns and Withdrawals

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